

Point Prevalence and Clinical Characteristics of Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder and Symptoms in Tuberous Sclerosis Complex: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis

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Abstract

Tuberous sclerosis complex (TSC) often co-occurs with neuropsychiatric disorders, although its association with obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD) and obsessive-compulsive symptoms (OCS) has received limited attention. This systematic review and meta-analysis aimed to calculate the pooled point prevalence estimate of OCD and OCS in individuals with TSC as well as descriptively synthesise the clinical characteristics within this population. MEDLINE, Embase, Ovid Full Text, and PsycINFO were searched through April 2025, supplemented with backward and forward citation searching. Two reviewers independently screened full-text records to identify peer-reviewed English-language studies with primary data on OCD/OCS in individuals with TSC regardless of age. The included studies were then critically appraised via the Mixed-Methods Appraisal Tool. Data were extracted and synthesised using a random-effects meta-analysis of proportions, a meta-regression of assessment type, and subgroup analyses of age and genotype. Heterogeneity was quantified via I^2 and τ^2 . Sixteen studies met the eligibility criteria for the systematic review, of which 10 were included for the meta-analysis of proportions. The 10 studies ($n = 1,429$) produced a pooled point prevalence of 10.0% [95% CI: 5.2–18.3%; $I^2 = 87.6\%$; $\tau^2 = 0.711$; $p < 0.0001$]. Neither assessment type, age, nor genotype significantly affected the point prevalence estimate. Despite notable clinical characteristics and a significant association between TSC and OCD/OCS, no preregistration and considerable heterogeneity render these results as exploratory and requiring cautious interpretation. Future studies—with prospective designs and more-diverse participant sources—will ensure more precise prevalence estimates and increased generalisability.

Keywords: Tuberous sclerosis complex, TSC-associated neuropsychiatric disorders,

Obsessive-compulsive disorder, Systematic review, Meta-analysis

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Point Prevalence and Clinical Characteristics of Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder and Symptoms in Tuberous Sclerosis Complex: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis

Introduction

TSC: An Overview

Tuberous sclerosis complex (TSC) is a rare multi-system autosomal-dominant genetic disorder that can profoundly affect an individual's quality of life, yet remains under-treated (Zöllner et al., 2020). The disorder affects approximately 1 in 5,000–13,000 live births worldwide, with prevalence estimates varying by study design and sequencing methodology (Ebrahimi-Fakhari et al., 2018; Kingswood et al., 2017).

TSC presents with a wide range of clinical characteristics—whether genetic, morphological, neurological, or neuropsychiatric characteristics, amongst others (Curatolo et al., 2008; Vanclooster et al., 2022). These characteristics arise from mutations in either *TSC1* or *TSC2*, suppressor genes that encode the proteins, hamartin and tuberin, respectively (Dufner-Almeida et al., 2024). *TSC1* is located on chromosome 9q34 whereas *TSC2* is located on chromosome 16p13.

Together, *TSC1* and *TSC2* form an intracellular complex (Curatolo et al., 2015), which suppresses the mechanistic target of rapamycin (mTOR) protein complex. When mutation occurs, the *TSC1*-*TSC2* complex cannot suppress mTOR, which leads to hyperactive and dysregulated activity in the mTOR signalling pathway (Balthazard et al., 2025; Curatolo et al., 2015; Hallett et al., 2011). This in turn enables increased proliferation and dysregulated migration, producing the various lesions and abnormalities in cells and tissues throughout the body synonymous with TSC (Costa-Mattioli & Monteggia, 2013; Józwiak et al., 2025).

Across studies, 10-15% of individuals with TSC present no mutation in either *TSC1* or *TSC2* (Henske et al., 2016; Tyburczy et al., 2015). The lack of identifiable mutation likely

results from genetic mosaicism, intronic mutations, and limitations in genetic testing precision, rather than a third possible genetic mutation (Dufner-Almeida et al., 2024; Kingswood et al., 2017). Mosaicism is often associated with milder TSC phenotypes, although evidence is limited (Peron et al., 2018). Whether mosaicism or direct TSC1 or TSC2 mutations, these genetic and biological mechanisms can produce a wide variability of morphological manifestations and behavioural symptoms (Vanclooster et al., 2022).

Morphologically, TSC is characterised by benign tumours (hamartomas). (Ali & Mulita, 2025; Weinstock et al., 2024). Hamartomas often manifest in multiple organs, such as the skin, heart, kidneys, with the most severe manifestations occurring in the brain (Salussolia et al., 2019; Vanclooster et al., 2022). The hallmark brain hamartomas are cortical tubers—firm root-shaped growths in the gyri—which present in approximately 90% of individuals (Henske et al., 2016). Calcified tumours called subependymal giant cell astrocytomas (SEGA) are far less common, affecting 5–25% of individuals with TSC (A. B. Marcinkowska et al., 2023; Salussolia et al., 2019).

Clinically, TSC severity ranges from mild symptoms without functional impairments to severe multi-system neurological, neurodevelopmental, and neuropsychiatric conditions (Jansen et al., 2020; A. B. Marcinkowska et al., 2023; Zöllner et al., 2020). In TSC, the most common neurological condition is epilepsy. Epilepsy is a chronic neurological disorder marked by the predisposition to recurrent unprovoked seizures, or episodes of excessive synchronised neuronal activity in one or both brain hemispheres (Manole et al., 2023; Stafstrom & Carmant, 2015). Multiple clinical and systematic reviews show that epilepsy affects 66–93% of individuals and is highly associated with poor cognitive and behavioural outcomes (Hallett et al., 2011; A. B. Marcinkowska et al., 2023; Miszewska et al., 2021).

To date, the genetic and molecular mechanisms of TSC are well-characterised, with most research aimed at closing knowledge gaps related to their mechanistic role in

neurological development. However, their role in the development of neuropsychiatric disorders remains poorly understood (de Vries et al., 2015). Approximately 90% of individuals with TSC experience associated neuropsychiatric symptoms in their lifetime, yet only roughly 20% receive treatment (Gupta et al., 2024; Vanclooster et al., 2022). Therefore, there is an unmet need to better understand, assess, and treat the neuropsychiatric symptoms present in many individuals with TSC. The recent conception of *TSC-associated neuropsychiatric disorders (TAND)* has helped to close this persistent gap.

The Timeline of TAND

Introduced in 2012, TAND is an umbrella term for the various mental health-related symptoms that affect most individuals with TSC in their lifetime. As neuropsychiatric symptoms were under-assessed and under-treated, TAND was coined to promote a shared language and promote greater awareness, assessment, and treatment of these oft-overlooked symptoms (de Vries et al., 2015). The term comprises six interrelated levels of difficulties: behavioural, psychiatric, intellectual, academic, neuropsychological, and psychosocial.

At the behavioural level, clinicians screen observable difficulties or concerns, often identifying individuals “at risk” for future psychiatric diagnoses based on subclinical symptoms or preclinical biomarkers. Subclinical and preclinical concerns are typically measured via questionnaires.

At the psychiatric TAND level, clinicians assess the behavioural-level concerns against an individual’s overall development, considering all the experiences that make up their biopsychosocial profile. Typically, the individual’s symptoms are assessed using psychometric tests aligned with standard diagnostic criteria published in the *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fifth Edition (DSM-5)* or the *International Classification of Diseases, Eleventh Edition (ICD-11)*. These tests help determine whether symptom number, intensity, and duration meet DSM-5 or ICD-11 diagnostic thresholds.

The intellectual level of TAND assesses intellectual abilities through standardised IQ testing, while the academic level examines specific learning abilities (e.g., literacy and numeracy), particularly in young children (Vanclooster et al., 2022). The neuropsychological level captures specific cognitive deficits (e.g., memory), and the psychosocial level addresses difficulties in self-concept, family relationships, and community integration (de Vries, Wilde, et al., 2018).

To help clinicians assess these wide-ranging symptoms in a standardised and validated way, researchers developed the TAND Checklist (Chambers et al., 2025; Leclezio et al., 2015). Published in 2015, the TAND Checklist is a simple 12-item yes-or-no questionnaire designed to help individuals with TSC better understand their mental health-related symptoms. The checklist has also helped clinicians and researchers better characterise and address these challenges in both clinical and research settings. However, uptake has been limited: a recent scoping review found that only 3.5% of 200 TAND studies reported using the checklist (Vanclooster et al., 2022). Although follow-up studies confirm its reliability, concurrent validity is lower for cognitive domains compared with external measures (Boisclair et al., 2025).

The conceptualisation of TAND has nonetheless catalysed TAND research in the past decade (Vanclooster et al., 2022). This increase in TAND research was further exemplified in 2017 by the launch of the Tuberous Sclerosis registry to increase disease Awareness (TOSCA)—the largest registry of clinical case series data on TSC and TAND. With data from more than 2,000 individuals from 170 recruitment sites across 31 countries (Kingswood et al., 2017), many TAND research groups worldwide have used this growing registry to inform their research questions, which has yielded noteworthy insights. For instance, ASD (~21%) may be far less prevalent than previously estimated (50%) (Leclezio & De Vries, 2015). Additionally, mutations to TSC2 specifically confer greater risk for developing ASD when

co-occurring with an intellectual disability (ID) (de Vries, Belousova, Benedik, Carter, Cottin, et al., 2020). Both these findings are limited, however, by substantial missing data (~33%), which introduces non-response bias and limits generalisability to the broader TSC population.

Subsequent studies with complete datasets have replicated these associations, amongst others. Consistently, TSC2 genetic mutations, high cortical tuber count, infantile spasms, and early-onset epilepsy confer increased risk for poorer TAND outcomes (Dhawan et al., 2025; A. B. Marcinkowska et al., 2023; Osman et al., 2025). However, the evidence is not conclusive (Hulshof et al., 2022), and most research suggests no single factor is singularly necessary nor sufficient for developing any TAND (de Vries & Howe, 2007)). This shows that a more complex interaction of clinical characteristics likely underlies symptoms. This complexity can ultimately lead to treatment paralysis, an inability or unknowingness in clinicians to treat highly heterogenous TAND symptom profiles (Vanclooster et al., 2022).

To help ease treatment paralysis and tailor more suitable treatment approaches, a 2020 data-driven analysis identified seven “natural” TAND clusters (de Vries et al., 2021). Each TAND cluster relates to a common set of symptoms shared by many individuals with TSC. These include scholastic, neuropsychological, ASD-like, dysregulated behaviour, overactive/impulsive, mood/anxiety, and eat/sleep clusters.

While these clusters enhance understanding of common symptom constellations, they do not capture all TAND conditions. There is evidence, albeit limited, of TAND conditions that fall outside these clusters (Chung et al., 2011). For these conditions, there is a current gap in knowledge regarding their clinical characteristics and pooled prevalence estimates, and a risk they will be overlooked if future research prioritises the natural TAND clusters. Amongst these conditions are psychotic disorders, substance use disorders, and perhaps even less-studied obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD) (de Vries et al., 2015; Varghese et al., 2018).

To address this evidence gap, the present systematic review and meta-analysis examines OCD and undiagnosed obsessive-compulsive symptoms (OCS) in individuals with TSC.

OCD, OCS, and TSC: The Present Review

OCD is a chronic neuropsychiatric disorder characterised by obsessions and compulsions (Stein et al., 2019). Obsessions are recurring intrusive thoughts or mental images that cause distress. Compulsions are repetitive irrational behaviours performed to reduce such distress, also called rituals. Together, these symptoms can cause significant impairment in daily functioning and form the basis for diagnosis under the DSM-5 and ICD-11. The gold-standard measurement tool for OCD is the Yale-Brown Obsessive-Compulsive Scale (Y-BOCS), which has an adapted version for children (CY-BOCS) (Deacon & Abramowitz, 2005; Schulze et al., 2025). Even in non-TSC populations, OCD is historically underdiagnosed and under-treated (Pampaloni et al., 2022).

A recent large-scale world mental health survey of more than 26,000 adults with OCD (without TSC) found the 12-month prevalence in the general population was 3% (Stein et al., 2025). Factor analyses consistently identify four major OCD symptom dimensions: (1) contamination and cleaning, (2) harm, safety, and checking, (3) ordering or “just right” symmetry, and (4) unacceptable or taboo thoughts (Mataix-Cols et al., 2005; Thorsen et al., 2018). These dimensions appear to be stable across socioeconomic status (SES) and cultural contexts, despite idiosyncratic variation in specific symptom content (W. Hassan et al., 2024). Similar to many other TAND, OCD presentation and severity vary with age and most individuals show mild symptoms on the Y-BOCS (Fernández de la Cruz et al., 2013; Stein et al., 2025). Co-occurring conditions are common (roughly 71%) and typically include other TAND such as bipolar disorder (~23%) major depressive disorder (23–41%) (Sharma et al., 2021). Individuals with OCD are nearly eight times more likely to develop psychosis than healthy controls (Rowe et al., 2022).

Current understanding of OCD—and its phenomenology and biological markers—has developed considerably within the last few decades, allowing for better recognition, assessment, and treatment of associated symptoms (Stein et al., 2019). Part of these advances in understanding include subclinical OCS, which appear far more prevalent (20%) than previously estimated (~8%), although the newest estimate occurred during the COVID-19 pandemic and heterogeneity was extremely high (Pozza et al., 2024; Valleni-basile et al., 1996). Moreover, it appears that experiencing more symptom subtypes increases the risk that OCS develop into clinical OCD (Stein et al., 2025).

Both OCD and OCS show preliminary evidence of an association with TSC, although the evidence base is nascent. In the TOSCA baseline dataset, 6% of individuals with TSC had obsessions (Kingswood et al., 2017), which rose to 17% with co-occurring ID (de Vries, Belousova, Benedik, Carter, Cottin, et al., 2020). Meanwhile, a more recent study found no individuals with TSC and epilepsy had OCD, although this finding may be limited by a small sample size ($n = 38$) (Lee et al., 2024).

Despite the evidence scarcity, there is a biological plausibility for an association between OCD/OCS and TSC. First, similar to TSC, there is a strong association between epilepsy and an increased risk for OCD (Kwon et al., 2025). More specifically, epileptic seizures arising in the temporal lobe are repeatedly shown to occur at greater rates in individuals with OCD and an increased risk for developing clinical OCD in those with OCS (Kaplan, 2011). Additionally, although evidence is mixed, multiple genome-wide association studies have found genetic variants on chromosome 16p13.11 in OCD, which overlaps with the locus of the TSC2 gene associated with poorer TAND outcomes (Mahjani et al., 2022; McGrath et al., 2014).

Beyond shared mechanisms, the clinical need for review is substantial. OCD ranks among the top ten most disabling conditions worldwide in terms of quality-adjusted life years

lost (WHO), and co-occurrence with TSC may compound functional impairment (Pampaloni et al., 2022). Understanding its clinical characteristics is therefore essential to inform more effective assessment and treatment strategies.

One factor that may obscure accurate assessment is diagnostic overshadowing—a cognitive bias in which clinicians misattribute symptoms to an existing diagnosis rather than identifying a separate co-occurring condition (Hallyburton, 2022). In TSC, this bias is particularly prominent, which motivated the conceptualisation of TAND (Leclezio & de Vries, 2016). When present, diagnostic overshadowing can delay or prevent access to appropriate, targeted interventions for genuine co-occurring conditions. To address this risk, the present review considers both OCD and OCS. Focusing solely on diagnosed OCD risks excluding potentially many individuals with TSC and clinical-level OCS without a diagnosis because of diagnostic overshadowing.

Research focused on individuals with co-occurring OCD/OCS and TSC is crucial given their associated potential underlying biological mechanisms, common comorbidities, and altogether biological plausibility. However, no studies have systematically reviewed co-occurring OCD/OCS and TSC, which leaves a notable knowledge gap regarding their association (de Vries, Wilde, et al., 2018). This dissertation aims to systematically review and synthesise evidence on the prevalence and clinical characteristics of OCD and OCS in individuals with TSC. This aim will be investigated through one primary and one secondary research question:

- 1) What is the pooled point prevalence of OCD and OCS in individuals with TSC?
- 2) What clinical characteristics are associated with co-occurring TSC and OCD/OCS, and how do methodological or participant factors influence variations in these clinical characteristics?

Methods

This systematic review was conducted according to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analyses (PRISMA) guidelines to ensure transparent and complete reporting of research processes (Page, McKenzie, et al., 2021). The Cochrane Handbook was also consulted to improve methodological rigour (Higgins et al., 2024).

Eligibility Criteria

Rather than the conventional PICO method, which is tailored for randomised controlled trial research, the CoCoPop (condition-context-population) question formulation framework was used to develop eligibility criteria, as it is a standardised method more conducive to systematic reviews of observational research, commonly found in TAND, and meta-analyses of proportions (Munn et al., 2015, 2018). With CoCoPop, eligibility criteria were identified according to the condition, context, and population being studied.

Table 1

CoCoPop Question Formulation Framework for Eligibility Criteria

Condition	Tuberous sclerosis complex and obsessive-compulsive disorder as diagnosed by the <i>Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-5)</i> or <i>International Classification of Diseases (ICD-11)</i> , and obsessive-compulsive symptoms as measured by various screening tools.
Context	Clinics, registries, and surveys (inclusive of all participant sources and recruitment methods).
Population	Human participants of any age, geographic location, socioeconomic status, and cultural or ethnic background.

Eligibility criteria were set a priori to minimise selection bias (Higgins et al., 2024).

These criteria were established for title and abstract screening (Table 2) and expanded for full-text screening (Table 3). All studies required TAND keywords, primary data on TSC populations, and peer-reviewed publication to reduce selection bias. Additionally, studies were eligible if they investigated either OCD or OCS. This was to overcome possible diagnostic overshadowing, which might have yielded limited evidence if only OCD was

included (see Introduction). Studies were also eligible regardless of publication date, duration of follow-up, age of the participants, or research setting (e.g., clinic versus online survey). These over-inclusive eligibility criteria increased the sensitivity to capture enough studies relevant to perform meaningful descriptive and quantitative synthesis (Lagisz et al., 2025; Siddaway et al., 2019). Lastly, all studies had to be published in English. While this risks language bias and missing relevant data, reliable human translation was unavailable for this dissertation, and automated translation has questionable accuracy (Balk et al., 2013; Pieper & Puljak, 2021)

For the full-text eligibility stage, there were four notable exclusion criteria. First, studies about OCD-related disorders rather than OCS or OCD proper were excluded. Despite some similarities, OCD-related disorders typically show distinct functional and neuropsychological features that lie outside the scope of this review's research questions (Chamberlain et al., 2007; McKay, 2014). Second, studies focusing on repetitive behaviour in ASD rather than OCD were excluded. Although some evidence suggests ASD- and OCD-associated repetitive behaviours exist within a broader singular disorder (Dell'Osso et al., 2025), more consistent neurobiological and phenomenological evidence distinguishes OCD compulsions from ASD repetitive behaviours (Paula-Pérez, 2013; Ruzzano et al., 2015). Thus, omitting ASD-only data ensured this review fulfilled its pre-specified rationale to focus on the TSC-OCD knowledge gap. Third, this review excluded studies in which OCD, and its prevalence, was not distinguished amongst the broader class of anxiety disorders. This maintained some specificity amongst screening results for meaningful comparison, as well as respected the most-recent DSM-5 and ICD-11 categorisations (Chamberlain et al., 2007). Finally, grey literature (e.g., conference proceedings) was excluded because of insufficient methodological data and missing peer-review (Martin et al., 2005; Paez, 2017).

Table 2

Title and Abstract Screening Eligibility Criteria

Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Studies published in peer-reviewed scientific journals.	“TSC” not related to tuberous sclerosis complex (e.g., thiosemicarbazone).
TAND-level keywords included in the resource subject.	TSC related to non-TAND topics (e.g., TSC genetic mechanisms only).
Any research methodology or study design containing primary TAND data.	Literature reviews, systematic reviews, meta-analyses, book chapters, and conference proceedings, without primary TAND data.
Must reference relevant TSC and OCD/OCS study populations.	“OCD” not related to obsessive-compulsive disorder (e.g., organisational change and development).
Must be published in English.	

Table 3*Full-Text Screening Eligibility Criteria*

Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Studies published in peer-reviewed scientific journals.	“TSC” not related to tuberous sclerosis complex (e.g., thiosemicarbazone).
TAND-level keywords included in the resource subject.	TSC related to non-TAND topics (e.g., TSC genetic mechanisms only).
Any research methodology or study design containing primary TAND data.	Literature reviews, systematic reviews, meta-analyses, book chapters, conference proceedings, without primary TAND data.
Must reference relevant TSC and OCD/OCS study populations.	“OCD” not related to obsessive-compulsive disorder (e.g., organisational change and development).
Must be published in English.	OCD-related disorders (e.g., trichotillomania) rather than OCD proper.
Full-text and results must be available/retrievable.	Repetitive or compulsive behaviours associated with autism spectrum disorders rather than OCD. OCD not related to TAND topics. OCD grouped within, and its prevalence undistinguished from, the broader cluster of anxiety disorders. Grey literature without comprehensive methodology and data (e.g., conference abstracts).

Information Sources

Studies were identified through Ovid, a platform comprising multiple scientific literature databases. Within Ovid, search results were limited to four databases:

Journals@Ovid Full Text (1993–31 March 2025), Embase (1974–31 March 2025), Ovid MEDLINE ALL (1946–31 March 2025), and PsycINFO (1967–March 2025 Week Four). As shown, a minimum of four databases searched yields an estimated sensitivity of 90% for retrieving observational studies, which comprise most TAND research (Metelli & Chaimani, 2020). MEDLINE and Embase were included, as they are amongst the two largest databases in terms of unique and total records (Bramer et al., 2017; Higgins et al., 2024). PsycINFO was specifically searched to yield studies from mental health disciplines that might be unavailable in more general databases. The databases were searched once (1 April 2025), after which, studies were then imported into Covidence—an online software that streamlines the systematic review process.

Two rounds of backward and forward citation searching were performed on reference lists of all included studies yielded from the Ovid database search to potentially find additional studies to help answer the research questions (Page, Moher, et al., 2021). Citation searching was conducted primarily using the citation index database, Scopus, and when necessary, the search engine Google Scholar (<https://scholar.google.com/>), and website ResearchGate (<https://www.researchgate.net/>). It was completed on 6 June 2025.

Grey literature was initially searched via registers and repositories but later excluded post-hoc (see Eligibility Criteria). For the complete list of specific registers and repositories searched for grey literature, and their results, see Appendix 1.

Search Strategy

Search terms were grouped by the two main conditions of interest—TSC and OCD/OCS. Synonyms were compiled after analysing systematic reviews published in peer-reviewed literature (Shobeiri et al., 2024; Vanclooster et al., 2022; Zöllner et al., 2020). While this review’s search strategy was not formally peer-reviewed by specific tools (e.g., the PRESS checklist), it was content-validated and approved by the lab supervisor, who has

extensive research experience in TSC- and TAND-related fields. No limits, filters, or restrictions were applied to the search in Ovid (e.g., by publication date or study design). The TSC search terms, OCD/OCS search terms, and Boolean operators are listed below (Table 4). For the full line-by-line search results, see Appendix 2.

Table 4

TSC and OCD/OCS Search Terms in Ovid

Set	Search algorithm
1.	("Tuberous sclerosis" OR "Tuberous sclerosis complex" OR "Tuberose sclerosis" OR "Sclerosis tuberosa" OR "TSC associated neuropsychiatric disorders.")
2.	("OCD" OR "Obsessi*" OR "Compulsi*" OR "OCD-like" OR "Ritual*" OR "neuros*.")
3.	1 AND 2

Note. The combined results were before de-duplication.

Variations in TSC terms, "tuberose sclerosis" and "sclerosis tuberosa," were included to account for historical names and variant spellings. Likewise, for OCD/OCS, variants were used to account for historical names, whereby "neuros*" referred to obsessive-compulsive neurosis (or neuroses), common to early twentieth-century psychological research (Steinberg et al., 2017). Asterisks enabled truncation, which accounted for varying suffixes and yielded more comprehensive results. The last search was performed on 1 April 2025.

Study Selection

Titles and abstracts were screened by a single reviewer, based on pre-specified title and abstract screening eligibility criteria (Table 2). Given the substantial number of studies yielded and the time constraints of this review's deadline, dual independent review was unfeasible. If OCD- or OCS-related keywords were found, they were rated as "Yes" in Covidence and included for full-text screening. Whereas if any other TAND-related keywords (e.g., ASD) were in the resource subject, they were rated "Maybe" in Covidence and also

included for full-text screening. Retaining possibly relevant “Maybe” studies was to be over-inclusive and avoid missing studies with relevant data only expanded upon in the full text.

After title and abstract screening, far fewer studies remained for full-text screening, which enabled dual independent review to improve selection consistency and minimise (specific) bias. Dual independent review was performed by the author and a second reviewer within Covidence, which has built-in blinding conditions for inter-rater reliability.

After both reviewers completed full-text screening, inter-rater reliability was calculated to measure the agreement level between the two reviewers using the standard measure, Cohen’s κ , calculated in the SPSS software (double check the correct one) (Belur et al., 2021). Any disagreements that could not be resolved between the two reviewers were reconciled through arbitration by the lab supervisor.

Data Extraction

Data extraction was performed in Covidence to help reduce data entry errors (Taylor et al., 2021). The Covidence Extraction 2 template was chosen as it has a more unstructured (customisable) format, which better suited the observational data commonly found in TAND research. It was customised according to Cochrane Handbook recommendations, adapted to answer the research questions related to this review’s research questions (Higgins et al., 2024).

Data extraction was a resource-intensive task and, given time constraints, was limited to a single reviewer. To help minimise cognitive bias and improve accuracy, the generative artificial intelligence (GenAI) Microsoft Copilot was used as a modified second reviewer. Copilot was selected as it maintains relatively high accuracy and is recommended by the University of Birmingham.

All fields were first completed by a human reviewer (the author). After this, Copilot was prompted to review three data fields: 1) methods to control for confounding, selection

biases, and information biases; 2) methods of data aggregation; 3) measurement tools used. Recent and consistent evidence shows GenAI is prone to misrepresent or hallucinate (fabricate) information (Kim et al., 2025). As a result, the author reviewed the results from Copilot against the source study to ensure any additional findings were accurate.

Data extraction occurred between 22–27 June 2025. Included below is an abridged list of extracted data (Table 5). For the full data extraction form, see Appendix 3.

Table 5

The Abridged Data Extraction Form

1. Report: Author(s), publication year, DOI.
2. Study: Design type, sample characteristics, eligibility criteria, diagnostic criteria, aims, sample size (total versus individuals with target symptoms), key conclusions.
3. Participants: Children and adults with TSC, onset of OCD or OCS), all TAND-level symptoms (e.g., behavioural, intellectual, etc.).
4. Research design and other features: participant recruitment method, start and end dates, statistical analysis methods, methods to control confounding and biases, funding sources, conflicts of interest.

Quality Assessment

This review conducted quality assessment before data extraction to mitigate cognitive bias of greater appraisal toward studies with significant results. Based on guidance from the lab supervisor, the Mixed Method Appraisal Tool (MMAT), 2018 Version, was used for quality assessment (Hong et al., 2018). While most TAND literature has varying quantitative designs (e.g., cohort studies versus case reports), the MMAT can flexibly appraise these through related criteria sets, ensuring some standardisation under one tool (Hong et al., 2019; Souto et al., 2015).

Adaptations to MMAT ratings followed those made in the (Vanclouster et al., 2022) scoping review, in which a quantitative scoring system was introduced to calculate category and overall quality assessment scores, enabling more standardised comparison of quality between study designs. Domains could be answered as “No,” “Partial Yes,” or “Yes,” which corresponded to ratings of 0, 0.5, and 1, respectively. As all studies have the same two screening questions, plus each category has five domain questions, the maximum score for a study was $7/7 = 1.00$. From this, a “traffic-light” approach categorised study quality by overall score, where scores <0.5 = low quality, scores ≥ 0.5 to <0.75 = medium quality, and scores ≥ 0.75 = high quality (Table 7).

Quality assessment was first performed independently by the lead author, after which, an alternate reviewer independently assessed quality for 25% of studies given time constraints. Inter-rater reliability was calculated using the standard Cohen’s κ in SPSS. More specifically, inter-rater reliability was calculated from respective scores on individual domains—rather than solely the overall score. This approach could then catch disagreements on specific domains (e.g., 0 vs. 1 on criteria 3.4) that would have otherwise been masked if studies received the same overall score (e.g., 0.86), allowing for more detailed comparison. The studies selected for inter-rater reliability were done so randomly via an online listed item generator.

Data Synthesis & Analysis

No formal protocol was pre-registered for this systematic review and meta-analysis, as it was not required for the dissertation. While most meta-analytic processes were planned a priori, the absence of pre-registration prevents this verification and introduces the risk of cognitive bias. The methods must therefore be considered post-hoc, while the results are limited to being hypothesis-generating, or exploratory, in nature (Page, Moher, et al., 2021).

The pooled point prevalence of OCD/OCS in TSC was the primary effect measure. Studies lacking raw prevalence numbers were omitted from the meta-analysis. Calculating odds ratios and mean differences was infeasible due to absent control groups.

Studies were eligible for pooling if they reported dichotomous data for both the number of individuals with TSC and co-occurring OCD or OCS (x_i), and a total TSC sample size (y_i) with $n > 1$. Proportions (x_i/y_i) were logit-transformed to stabilise variance and accommodate any proportions near 0 or 1 (Barker et al., 2021). Then, the within-study variance, between-study variance, 95% CIs, and prediction intervals were computed and back-transformed into proportions for ease of interpretation.

This systematic review and meta-analysis reported five tables and six figures (see Results):

- Study characteristics (Table 5)
- MMAT quality assessment (Table 7)
- Meta-regression (Table 8)
- Subgroup analyses (Table 9)
- Leave-one-out influence analysis (Table 10)
- Forest plot for the meta-analysis of proportions (Fig. 2)
- Baujat plot for heterogeneity and outlier studies (Fig. 3)
- Doi plot for the risk of reporting bias (Fig. 4)
- Contour-enhanced funnel plot as a sensitivity check (Appendix 4).

While funnel plots are the standard approach to presenting reporting bias when $k \geq 10$, they are poor at capturing bias in meta-analyses of proportions (Cheema et al., 2022). As a result, a newer and less-standard Doi plot was selected as a primary analysis of risk of publication bias, as it has shown mixed to positive effects in measuring reporting bias during

prevalence studies, although it too may lack precision when $k \approx 10$, and thus, requires cautious interpretation (Schwarzer et al., 2024).

All meta-analysis calculations were conducted using *R* (version 4.5.0, 2025; Appendices 5-11) using random-effects models with Hartung-Knapp-Sidik-Jonkman (HKSJ) 95% CIs. A random-effects model was used for all analyses to better account for the varying true effects across studies with different designs and sizes, assuming no single true effect (unlike fixed-effects models) (Borenstein, 2009). Multiple simulation studies have shown that whenever heterogeneity is present (τ^2 is > 0), as was expected in this study, random-effects models balanced estimates and increased generalisability (check generalisability). Meanwhile, 95% confidence intervals (CIs) were calculated as they are standard range for this data type, while the HKSJ method was chosen post-hoc for its more conservative CI estimates in meta-analyses with few studies and high heterogeneity (IntHout et al., 2014).

Heterogeneity was quantified using the standard I^2 and τ^2 statistical parameters. I^2 is a relative parameter that specifically measures inconsistency, or the variability in effect estimates across studies not due to chance (Mellor, 2024). It was interpreted against Cochrane thresholds, where $I^2 < 40\%$ represents “low” heterogeneity and 75–100% may represent considerable heterogeneity, although these are non-empirical “rules of thumb” thresholds, and should therefore be interpreted cautiously (Higgins et al., 2024). Meanwhile, τ^2 is an absolute parameter that more directly measures between-study variance, or the dispersion of effect sizes across studies (IntHout et al., 2016). It was estimated using a restricted maximum likelihood (REML), selected for its robustness in recent simulation studies (Wang, 2023). As τ^2 is an absolute parameter, prediction intervals were then calculated to ease interpretation (Iaquinto et al., 2025). Prediction intervals estimate the range of effects that a randomly selected new study would fall within.

The potential causes of heterogeneity were measured using a univariable meta-regression, univariable subgroup analysis, and Baujat plot, with a leave-one-out influence analysis for sensitivity (Borenstein, 2009). These statistical tests were only conducted when the degrees of freedom ($df > 5$), to avoid overfitting and generating overly imprecise confidence intervals (Higgins et al., 2024). The univariable meta-regression specifically investigated how a single moderator (assessment type) influenced the pooled prevalence estimate. Meanwhile, the subgroup analysis investigated pre-specified moderators—age cohort (i.e., children, adults, or both) and genotype (e.g., TSC1, TSC2, or no mutation identified). ID and epileptic history were also pre-specified, but not performed, because of insufficient data. No other moderators were tested so as to avoid data dredging, the increased risk of false positives from running an increasing number of moderators (Thompson & Higgins, 2002). After this, a Baujat plot was generated to identify outlier studies that disproportionately affected heterogeneity and the overall pooled prevalence estimates. Finally, a leave-one-out influence analysis was conducted to identify if the removal of any single study substantially affects the pooled prevalence estimate or heterogeneity.

To measure the risk of reporting bias within studies, qualitative, graphical, and statistical investigations were used. Qualitative investigations comprised post-hoc indexing of the registry, ClinicalTrials.gov, to fill in missing data. Two grey literature sources previously excluded were reintegrated to strengthen the test results. Graphical investigations included visual inspection of the Doi plot (Figure 5). Finally, statistical investigations assessed reporting bias in the Doi plot via the LFK index. All these methodological approaches were conducted independently by the author.

Results

Study Selection

Database searches via Ovid yielded 3,603 records, with 3,310 records to screen after automated de-duplication (Fig. 4). Sixty full-text documents were reviewed, amongst which, 11 were included (Bhattacharya et al., 2012; de Vries, Belousova, et al., 2018; Haddad et al., 2016; I. K. Hassan et al., 2014; S. Liu et al., 2020; A. Marcinkowska et al., 2022; Moavero, Voci, Romigi, et al., 2022; Pulsifer et al., 2007; Rao et al., 2015; Vlaskamp et al., 2017; Wilbur et al., 2017).

Grey literature searches (before post-hoc exclusion; see Methods) and citation searching added 964 de-duplicated results, yielding five additional studies (Ding et al., 2021; Fu et al., 2025; Moavero et al., 2022a; Muzykewicz et al., 2007; Ozgur et al., 2018). Overall, the combined total was therefore $k = 16$ studies. Amongst these 16 studies, 10 were included in the meta-analysis of proportions aimed at answering the primary research question (see Fig. 2; see Methods).

Forty-nine studies' full texts were excluded from database searches (see Appendix 12 for the list by exclusion reason). Primary exclusion reasons were non-OCD association ($n = 16$) and non-TSC association ($n = 9$), amongst others (Fig. 3).

Figure 1

PRISMA Flow Diagram

Full-text inter-rater reliability showed “substantial agreement” between the two reviewers (Cohen’s $\kappa = 0.76$, $p < 0.05$). All disagreements between reviewers, mainly on repetitive behaviours (OCD vs ASD), were resolved via in-person discussion. One notable disagreement centred upon the definition of primary research (de Vries, Belousova, et al., 2018), and was resolved by the independent arbiter, the lab supervisor, leading to the study’s inclusion.

Study Characteristics

Table 5 summarises the 16 studies included within this systematic review, detailing study information, methodology, participant demographics, genetic characteristics, and clinical characteristics.

Table 5*Characteristics of Studies Included in Systematic Review*

Author (year)	Study design	Country of participant origin	Participant source	Sex, % female	Genotype (% of <i>n</i> with OCD/OCS)	Age cohort	<i>n</i> with OCD or OCS	<i>n</i> with data for TAND analysis	OCD/OCS symptom dimension	OCD/OCS assessment tool (severity)	OCD diagnosis	Co-occurring conditions, TAND or otherwise (% of sample)
Bhattacharya et al. (2012)	Case report	India	Clinic	0%	NR	Adults	1	1	Contamination / washing	Y-BOCS (32/48)	Yes	Focal and generalised seizures; focal epileptiform discharges in right temporal lobe
de Vries et al. (2018) ^a	Analytic cross-sectional	International ^b	TOSCA registry	52%	TSC1 (16%) TSC2 (68%) NMI: (16%)	Mixed	100	714 ^c	NR	NR	No	NR
Ding et al. (2021) ^a	Analytic cross-sectional	China	Clinic	48%	TSC1 (33%) TSC2 (50%) NMI: (17%)	Children	6	95	NR	MINI-KID	Yes	ID (83%)
Fu et al. (2025) ^a	Analytic cross-sectional	China	Clinic	36%	NR	Children	2	47	NR	TAND Checklist	Yes	Drug-resistant epilepsy (100%)
Haddad et al. (2016)	Case report	Brazil	Clinic	0%	NR	Children	1	1	Contamination / washing	NR	Yes	Drug-responsive seizures; epileptogenic area in right temporal lobe; SEGA; learning difficulties
Hassan et al. (2014)	Case report	Australia	Clinic	0%	NR	Adults	1	1	Contamination / washing	NR	No	ID; psychosis; drug-responsive focal and generalised seizures; pericortical tubers
Liu et al. (2020) ^a	Analytic cross-sectional	United States	TS Alliance	56%	NR	Adults	3	16	NR	TAND Checklist	No	NR
Marcinkowska et al. (2022) ^a	Descriptive cross-sectional	Poland	Clinic	52%	NR	Adults	3	100	NR	TAND Checklist	Yes	Epilepsy (67%)
Moavero et al. (2022a) ^a	Descriptive cross-sectional	Italy	Italian TS Association	NR	NR	Children	17	177	NR	Team-generated questionnaire	Yes	NR

Author (year)	Study design	Country of participant origin	Participant source	Sex, % female	Genotype (% of <i>n</i> with OCD/OCS)	Age cohort	<i>n</i> with OCD or OCS	<i>n</i> with data for TAND analysis	OCD/OCS symptom dimension	OCD/OCS assessment tool (severity)	OCD diagnosis	Co-occurring conditions, TAND or otherwise (% of sample)
Moavero et al. (2022b) ^a	Descriptive cross-sectional	Italy	Italian TS Association	NR	NR	Adults	17	114	NR	Team-generated questionnaire	Yes	NR
Muzykewicz et al. (2007) ^a	Retrospective cohort	United States	Clinic	53%	TSC2 (100%)	Mixed	1	43 ^c	NR	NR	Yes	NR
Ozgur et al. (2018)	Case report	Turkey	Clinic	0%	NR	Children	1	1	Safety and taboo / Reassurance seeking	C-YBOCS (40/40)	Yes	Drug-responsive epilepsy; hamartomas in right temporal lobe
Pulsifer et al. (2007) ^a	Descriptive cross-sectional	United States	Clinic	67%	NR	Adults	17	42	NR	SCL-90-R (61 ±12 SD)	No	Epilepsy (65%)
Rao et al. (2015)	Case report	India	Clinic	0%	NR	Adults	1	1	Contamination / washing	Y-BOCS (20/40)	Yes	Organic psychosis; drug-responsive epilepsy; cortical tubers
Vlaskamp et al. (2017)	Single-case experimental	Netherlands	Clinic	100%	TSC1 (100%)	Adults	1	1	NR	RBS-R (10)	No	ASD (PDD-NOS); ID; subcortical tubers; drug-resistant focal and generalised seizures
Wilbur et al. (2017) ^a	Descriptive cross-sectional	Canada	Clinic	49%	NR	Children	5	81	NR	NR	No	NR

Note. ASD = autism spectrum disorder; C-YBOCS = Children's Yale-Brown Obsessive-compulsive Scale; ID = intellectual disability; MINI-KID = Mini International Neuropsychiatric Interview for Children; N/A = not applicable to study design; NR = not reported; OCD = obsessive-compulsive disorder; OCS = obsessive-compulsive symptoms; PDD-NOS = pervasive developmental disorder not otherwise specified; RBS-R = Repetitive Behaviour Scale-Revised; SCL-90-R = Symptom Checklist-90-Revised; TAND = tuberous sclerosis complex-associated neuropsychiatric disorders; TOSCA = Tuberous Sclerosis registry to increase disease Awareness TS = tuberous sclerosis; Y-BOCS = Yale-Brown Obsessive-compulsive Scale.

^a = Study included in main meta-analysis

^b = Included participants from Australia, Austria, Belgium, Brazil, Canada, China, Czechia, Denmark, Estonia, France, Germany, Greece, India, Israel, Italy, Japan, South Korea, Latvia, Lithuania, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, South Africa, Spain, Sweden, Taiwan, Thailand, Turkey, United Kingdom, United States.

^c = Different from total study sample size (i.e., did not include participants for which TAND data was unavailable)

Studies are ordered alphabetically by lead author last name and by publication date where necessary.

Study Design and Context

Amongst the 16 studies, cross-sectional designs predominated ($k = 9$; 53%). More specifically, four were analytic cross-sectional studies while five were descriptive cross-sectional studies, based on MMAT criteria (see Methods). Other design types included case reports ($k = 5$), a retrospective cohort ($k = 1$), and a single-case experiment ($k = 1$).

There were 35 countries of participant origin represented within this systematic review, 25 of which were only represented in the lone international study (de Vries, Belousova, et al., 2018). Excluding this study ($k = 15$), the 10 countries of participant origin were the United States ($k = 3$), China ($k = 2$), India ($k = 2$), Italy ($k = 2$), Australia ($k = 1$), Brazil ($k = 1$), Canada ($k = 1$), Netherlands ($k = 1$), Poland ($k = 1$), and Turkey ($k = 1$).

Most studies recruited participants from clinics ($k = 12$, 75%), while the rest recruited participants from various TSC registries ($k = 4$; 25%). No studies recruited participants via surveys. Additionally, most studies were performed in a single centre ($k = 15$; 94%), while only one study was performed across multiple centres (de Vries, Belousova, et al., 2018).

The total sample size of participants was 1,435 across the 16 studies (mean of 90 per study), which ranged from $n = 16$ (A. J. Liu et al., 2020) to $n = 714$ (de Vries, Belousova, et al., 2018). Nearly half (49.8%) of all participants within this systematic review came from the de Vries et al. (2018) study.

Demographics and Genotype

Eight studies sampled solely adults (50%), six sampled solely children (37.5%), and two sampled a mix of children and adults (12.5%). Genotype data was limited to $k = 4$ studies (de Vries, Belousova, et al., 2018; Ding et al., 2021; Muzykewicz et al., 2007; Vlaskamp et al., 2017). In two of these studies, OCD or OCS occurred only in individuals with a TSC1 genetic variant; however, each study only featured $n = 1$. In studies with $n > 1$ ($k = 2$), 67% of

individuals with OCD or OCS had a TSC2 variant (de Vries, Belousova, et al., 2018; Ding et al., 2021). Across these same two studies, 16% of individuals had no identifiable mutation.

Assessment Tools

Eight assessment tools were used to measure OCD and OCS in individuals with TSC. In studies with participants with diagnosed OCD, $k = 3$ studies used either the gold-standard Y-BOCS or C-YBOCS, $k = 3$ studies used the TAND Checklist, and $k = 1$ used the validated MINI-KID. Both studies by Moavero et al. (2022a; 2022b) used a non-validated team-generated questionnaire to measure individuals with diagnosed OCD. Conversely, amongst the $k = 4$ studies that strictly examined OCS, $k = 2$ used the TAND Checklist, $k = 1$ used the RBS-R, and $k = 1$ used the SCL-90-R.

Clinical OCD and OCS

Amongst the 16 studies, 10 studies (62.5%) recorded individuals with diagnosed OCD versus six studies (37.5%) of OCS. Notably, diagnosed OCD was reported in 80% of case reports ($k = 4/5$) versus 50% of cross-sectional studies ($k = 5/10$). Diagnosed OCD was present in 67% of clinic-based studies ($k = 8/12$), compared to 50% of registry-based studies ($k = 2/4$). Notably, in clinic-based studies with $n > 1$, OCS rates were 6.2% in children versus 40% in adults, although both were limited to one study each (Pulsifer et al., 2007; Wilbur et al., 2017).

Most studies did not report continuous data. Symptom severity was reported in 5/16 studies (~31%), of which, most were case reports ($k = 4$). Reported Y-BOCS/C-YBOCS ($k = 3$) scores were 20, 32, and 40, which indicates moderate, moderate-severe, and severe, respectively (see Table 5 note for possible misrepresentation) (Pampaloni et al., 2022). The SCL-90-R score was 61 (± 12 SD), which indicates clinical significance (Pulsifer et al., 2007). Finally, the RBS-R score was 10 for compulsive behaviour (no thresholds).

Meanwhile, symptom dimensions were reported in only 5/16 studies (~31%). All five studies were case reports. In four of the five case reports (80%), individuals presented with the contamination/washing symptom dimension (see Introduction). In the remaining case report, the individual reported symptoms related to the safety and taboo dimensions. This lone individual with safety/taboo obsessions was the same individual who scored the highest on the Y-BOCS (40/40) (Ozgun et al., 2018).

Table 6

Co-Occurring Conditions in Individuals with TSC and OCD/OCS

Domain	Prevalence, k (%)
Morphological (SEGA, pericortical tubers)	$k = 6/16$ (37.5%)
Epilepsy (focal and generalised seizures, epileptiform discharges)	$k = 9/16$ (56.3%)
Psychosis	$k = 2/16$ (12.5%)
ASD	$k = 1/16 =$ (6.25%)
ID	$k = 2/16 =$ (12.5%)

Co-occurring clinical or morphological conditions were reported in $k = 11/16$ studies (69%), of which were comprised of $k = 5$ case reports, $k = 4$ cross-sectional studies, and $k = 1$ single-case experimental study. Studies with larger sample sizes had reduced description of co-occurring conditions compared to studies with $n = 1$ ($k = 6$).

Only $k = 1$ study reported SEGA presence (Haddad et al., 2016). No studies reported on the size and number of cortical tubers, but $k = 3$ case reports broadly localised them to the cortex (Rao et al., 2015), the subcortex (Vlaskamp et al., 2017), and the right temporal lobe (Ozgun et al., 2018).

As far as other TAND, nine of the 10 studies (90%) that reported neuroimaging methods (90%) found that participants experienced comorbid seizures, epileptiform discharges, and/or epilepsy. More specifically, $k = 2$ studies found epileptic occurred in the right temporal lobe (Bhattacharya et al., 2012; Haddad et al., 2016), while a third study found

hamartomas in the same region (Ozgur et al., 2018). In the lone case report of an individual with TSC and OCS only, there was no co-occurrence of right temporal lobe disturbances reported (I. K. Hassan et al., 2014).

Quality Assessment

Table 7

MMAT Quality Assessment of Included Studies

Author (year)	Score (0–1.00)	Comments
Bhattacharya et al. (2012)	0.29	4.1 Non-probability sampling not relevant to answer research question. 4.2 Sample of $n = 1$ is not representative of target population. 4.3 4.4 Complete data exists on the subject. 4.5 Statistical analysis was not reported.
de Vries et al. (2018) ^a	0.64	3.1 Large sample of 2216 participants from TOSCA cohort is representative of general TSC population. 3.2 The variables are clearly defined; TAND Checklist, which has strong external validity. 3.3 Incomplete outcome data (32%). 3.4 Few efforts to control against confounders. 3.5 No exposure status changes during study, therefore exposure occurred as intended.
Ding et al. (2021) ^a	1.00	3.1 Large sample of 95 children of wide 6-16 age range is representative of paediatric TSC population. 3.2 Examined TSC1 or TSC2 gene mutations; Chinese translation of the reliable and validated MINI-KID assessment of TAND. 3.3 Complete outcome data (81%). 3.4 Children with TAND matched to control group by age and sex. 3.5 No changes in exposure status during study, therefore the exposure occurred as intended.
Fu et al. (2025) ^a	1.00	3.1 Moderate-sized sample of 47 children of wide 6-18 age range is representative of paediatric TSC population. 3.2 Official Chinese translation of the validated TAND Checklist; neuropsychologists evaluated TAND symptoms. 3.3 Complete outcome data (100%). 3.4 Matched epilepsy participants and controls by age, sex, and genotype. 3.5 No changes in exposure status during study, therefore the exposure occurred as intended.
Haddad et al. (2016)	0.21	4.1 Non-probability sampling not relevant to answer research question. 4.2 Sample of $n = 1$ is not representative of target population. 4.3 OCD tested using reliable and validated C-YBOCS, TSC with MRI. 4.4 Complete data does not exist on the subject. 4.5 Statistical analysis was not reported.
Hassan et al. (2014)	0.29	4.1 Non-probability sampling not relevant to answer research question. 4.2 Sample of $n = 1$ is not representative of target population. 4.3 Appropriate measures for TSC, but not for OCS. 4.4 Complete data does not exist on the subject. 4.5 Statistical analysis was not reported.
Liu et al. (2020)	0.86	3.1 Small sample of 16 older adults (mean age ≈ 47) without ID is not very representative of adult TSC population. 3.2 TAND Checklist used to measure behavioural-level OCS. 3.3 Complete outcome data (89%). 3.4 Matched individuals with TSC to age-matched healthy controls. 3.5 No changes in exposure status during study, therefore the exposure occurred as intended.
Marcinkowska et al. (2022) ^a	0.79	4.1 Non-probability sampling not relevant to answer research question. 4.2 Sample of $n = 100$ adults with TSC, with and without epilepsy and ID, is large, diverse, and relatively representative of general adult TSC population. 4.3 OCD diagnoses measured using validated TAND Checklist. 4.4 Possible undisclosed risk of nonresponse bias. 4.5 Multivariate analysis was appropriate to answer research question.
Moavero et al. (2022a) ^a	0.86	4.1 Non-probability sampling not relevant to answer research question. 4.2 Sample of 177 children is large and representative of target paediatric TSC population. 4.3 Team-generated online self-report questionnaire captures broad symptoms, although unvalidated. 4.4 Risk of nonresponse bias was low. 4.5 Uni- and multi-variate binary linear regression was appropriate to answer research question.

Author (year)	Score (0–1.00)	Comments
Moavero et al. (2022b) ^a	0.86	4.1 Non-probability sampling not relevant to answer research question. 4.2 Sample of 114 adults is large and representative of target adult TSC population. 4.3 Team-generated online self-report questionnaire captures broad symptoms, although unvalidated. 4.4 Risk of nonresponse bias was low. 4.5 Logistic regression model was appropriate to answer research question.
Muzykewicz et al. (2007) ^a	0.86	3.1 Large sample 241 children and adults is representative of general TSC population. 3.2 TAND screened by two psychiatrists affiliated with TSC research. Diagnostic tools were not specified. 3.3 Nearly complete outcome data (79%). 3.4 Logistic regression model controlled against confounders. 3.5 No changes in exposure status during study, therefore the exposure occurred as intended.
Ozgur et al. (2018)	0.57	4.1 Non-probability sampling not relevant to answer research question. 4.2 Sample of $n = 1$ is not representative of target population. 4.3 OCD tested using reliable and validated Y-BOCS, TSC with MRI. 4.4 Complete data exists on the subject. 4.5 Statistical analysis was not reported.
Pulsifer et al. (2007) ^a	0.86	4.1 Non-probability sampling not relevant to answer research question. 4.2 Sample of $n = 42$ is relatively small and only included adults with TSC but without ID does not accurately reflect the general TSC population. 4.3 Measured OCS using the SCL-90-R, which has reduced validity. 4.4 Nonresponse bias was moderate (31%). 4.5 One-way ANOVA to control against confounders, although no multivariate analysis to control overlapping covariates.
Rao et al. (2015)	0.29	4.1 Non-probability sampling not relevant to answer research question. 4.2 Sample of $n = 1$ is not representative of target population. 4.3 OCD tested using reliable and validated Y-BOCS, TSC with MRI. 4.4 Complete data exists on the subject. 4.5 Statistical analysis was not reported.
Vlaskamp et al. (2017)	0.79	3.1 Single-case study is not reflective of target TSC population. 3.2 RBS-R is a validated measured and administered appropriately by a treating psychiatrist. 3.3 Complete data was reported at all time points. 3.4 Statistical measures were not used to control confounders, although ABA treatment approach was used. 3.5 No changes in exposure status during study, therefore the exposure occurred as intended.
Wilbur et al. (2017) ^a	0.71	4.1 Non-probability sampling not relevant to answer research question. 4.2 Moderate sized ($n = 81$) mixed sample of children and adults is more representative of the general TSC population. 4.3 Measures were appropriate and conducted by trained psychiatrists and neurologists. 4.4 Nonresponse bias was low for most measures, except genotype data. 4.5 No statistical analysis was not reported.

Note. Scoring criteria adapted from the Mixed Methods Appraisal Test (MMAT) recommendations and the Vanclooster et al. (2022) study: <0.5 = Low quality; $\geq 0.5 - <0.75$ = Medium quality; ≥ 0.75 = High quality. Studies are sorted alphabetically by lead author last name, and by date of publication when necessary. For the individual scores for each domain, see Appendix 13.

Studies are ordered alphabetically by lead author last name and by publication date where necessary.

^a = Study included in main meta-analysis

According to MMAT criteria, all of the 16 studies were quantitative (see Appendix 14). Ten studies (62.5%) were categorised as quantitative descriptive (category 4). These included descriptive cross-sectional studies and case reports. Meanwhile, six studies (37.5%) were categorised as quantitative non-randomised (category 3), which included analytic cross-sectional studies, a retrospective cohort study, and a single-case experimental study. The overall mean quality ($k = 16$) was 0.71 (as medium quality). Inter-rater reliability showed “moderate agreement” between the two reviewers (Cohen’s $\kappa = 0.76$, $p < 0.05$) No studies were omitted for low-quality. Finally, no disagreements required a third-party arbiter.

Meta-Analysis

Of the initial 16 studies included in the systematic review, five case reports and one single-case experimental study were excluded from the meta-analysis of proportions (see Methods; Furuya-Kanamori et al., 2021). Thus, $k = 10$ studies were included (see Fig. 2).

The mean MMAT score for the 10 studies was 0.84 (high quality; low risk of bias). All the studies were included in all statistical tests, except for the subgroup analysis by genotype, of which there were only three studies with sufficient data (de Vries, Belousova, et al., 2018; Ding et al., 2021; Muzykewicz et al., 2007).

Pooled Point Prevalence Estimate

To address the first research question (see Introduction), a meta-analysis of proportions was conducted. In this meta-analysis of proportions, the pooled point prevalence estimate of OCD and OCS in individuals with TSC was 10.0% [95% CI: 5.2–18.3% (HKSJ)]. There was significant heterogeneity ($p < 0.0001$), with considerable inconsistency ($I^2 = 87.6\%$) and high between-study variance ($\tau^2 = 0.771$; SE = 0.49) (Higgins et al., 2024). The prediction interval was 1.4–45.8%.

Figure 2

Pooled Point Prevalence Estimate of TSC and Co-Occurring OCD and OCS

Note. I^2 = heterogeneity inconsistency. τ^2 = between-study variance. CI = confidence interval. HKSJ = Hartung-Knapp-Sidik-Jonkman confidence interval. PI = prediction interval.

$p < 0.0001$

Studies are ordered alphabetically by lead author last name and by publication date where necessary.

Meta-Regression

Assessment type was the only viable moderator ($df > 5$) for meta-regression (Table 8). As noted, assessment type referred to whether participants within each given study had received a formal OCD diagnosis or were only assessed on behavioural symptoms without such a diagnosis.

There were four studies ($k = 4$) that only assessed OCS (de Vries, Belousova, et al., 2018; A. J. Liu et al., 2020; Pulsifer et al., 2007; Wilbur et al., 2017). When this group was isolated, the pooled point prevalence increased to 17.2% [95% CI: 7.6%–34.4%], or roughly 28 % points. This contrasted with studies ($k = 6$) of individuals with diagnosed OCD, where the isolated prevalence was 6.6% [95% CI: 3–13.9%] (Ding et al., 2021; Fu et al., 2025; Marcinkowska et al., 2022; Moavero et al., 2022a; Moavero et al., 2022b; Muzykewicz et al., 2007). Both had identical I^2 (79.9%), τ^2 (0.532), and p-values ($p = 0.08$). The p-value was not statistically significant to reject the null hypothesis (i.e., that differences in prevalence between assessment types is due to random chance).

Table 8

Assessment Type Effects on TSC-OCD/OCS Pooled Point Prevalence Estimate

Moderator	Level	k	Prevalence (%)	95% CI (HKSJ)	I ² (%)	τ^2	p-value	Significant
Assessment type	Symptom	4	17.2	[7.6–34.4]	79.9	0.532	0.080	No
Assessment type	Diagnosis	6	6.6	[3.0–13.9]	79.9	0.532	0.080	No

Note. I^2 = heterogeneity inconsistency. τ^2 = between-study variance. CI = confidence interval. HKSJ = Hartung-Knapp-Sidik-Jonkman confidence interval.

Subgroup Analyses

Subgroup analyses (random effects) were performed for moderators not viable for meta-regression ($df < 10$). For this subgroup analysis, only subgroups that appeared in ≥ 3 studies were analysed. Age cohort and genotype were the only moderators that met these criteria. Conversely, the pre-specified ID and epileptic history moderators (see Methods) had insufficient data ($df < 5$), and risked overfitting, were excluded.

From the subgroup analysis, mixed age cohort samples ($k = 2$) had too few studies to generate interpretable CIs [95% CI: 0–100%] (de Vries, Belousova, et al., 2018; Muzykewicz et al., 2007). Meanwhile, adult-only cohorts ($k = 3$) yielded the highest pooled prevalence (15.2%), but likewise, did not yield meaningful CIs.

Similarly, analysis by genotype had few studies to pool from ($k = 3$). All three levels of genotype (TSC1, TSC2, and NMI) were reported by the same three studies (de Vries, Belousova, et al., 2018; Ding et al., 2021; Muzykewicz et al., 2007), which led to identical null I^2 and τ^2 heterogeneity values. Given the absent heterogeneity, the genotype moderator yielded far more precise CIs than the age cohort moderator. Overall, neither age cohort nor genotype subgroups yielded statistically significant p-values to explain the considerable heterogeneity in the main meta-analysis of proportions.

To complement these subgroup analyses, a Baujat plot analysis measured heterogeneity and outlier studies (Fig. 5).

Table 9

Age Cohort and Genotype Effects on TSC-OCD/OCS Pooled Point Prevalence Estimate

Moderator	Level	k	Prevalence (%)	95% CI (HKSJ)	I ² (%)	τ^2	p-value	Significant
Age cohort	child	4	7.7	[4.8–12.3]	1.1	0.002	0.402	No
Age cohort	adult	4	15.2	[2.3–57.6]	89.7	1.378	0.402	No
Age cohort	mixed	2	7.5	[0.0–100.0]	72.0	1.331	0.402	No
Genotype	TSC1 mutation	3	4.6	[2.2–9.4]	0.0	0.000	0.412	No
Genotype	TSC2 mutation	3	5.4	[4.6–6.2]	0.0	0.000	0.412	No
Genotype	No mutation identified	3	6.1	[3.1–11.5]	0.0	0.000	0.412	No

Note. I^2 = heterogeneity inconsistency. τ^2 = between-study variance. CI = confidence interval. HKSJ = Hartung-Knapp-Sidik-Jonkman confidence interval.

To further assess heterogeneity, a Baujat plot complemented the subgroup results, as visual inspection revealed minimal heterogeneity between most studies. Similar within-study prevalence estimates (magnitudes) were like the between-studies' pooled OCD/OCS prevalence, as depicted by clustering within the bottom-left quadrant. Only one study had both high heterogeneity and a high magnitude difference from the overall pooled prevalence estimate, indicative of an outlier study (Pulsifer et al., 2007). This study was retained to minimise bias.

Figure 3

Plotting Studies by their Magnitude and Heterogeneity

Note. Cochran's Q = heterogeneity chi-squared test.

Sensitivity Analysis

The post-hoc leave-one-out influence analysis substantiated the Baujat plot results (Table 10). No individual omission in which each study in the meta-analysis is systematically removed, one at a time, to calculate how its omission affects the pooled point prevalence estimate, CIs, and heterogeneity.

Table 10

Leave-One-Out Influence Analysis on TSC-OCD/OCS Pooled Point Prevalence Estimate

Removed study	Total N	LO Prevalence (%)	95% CI (HKSJ)	I^2 (%)	τ^2
de Vries et al. (2018)	714	9.4	[4.4–18.7]	83.4	0.841
Ding et al. (2021)	95	10.4	[5.0–20.4]	88.9	0.785
Fu et al. (2025)	47	10.7	[5.3–20.3]	88.6	0.719
Liu et al. (2020)	16	9.3	[4.5–18.2]	89.3	0.779
Marcinkowska et al. (2022)	100	11.3	[5.9–20.6]	86.6	0.606
Moavero et al. (2022a)	177	9.9	[4.6–19.8]	88.0	0.854
Moavero et al. (2022b)	114	9.3	[4.4–18.6]	87.8	0.825
Muzykewicz et al. (2007)	43	10.8	[5.6–19.9]	88.0	0.670
Pulsifer et al. (2007)	42	8.8	[5.4–14.0]	68.9	0.235
Wilbur et al. (2017)	81	10.4	[5.0–20.4]	89.0	0.780
Random-effects model (k = 10)	1429	10.0	[5.2–18.3]	87.6	0.711

Note. Studies are ordered alphabetically by lead author last name, and by publication date where necessary. I^2 = heterogeneity inconsistency. τ^2 = between-study variance. LO = left out. CI = confidence interval. HKSJ = Hartung-Knapp-Sidik-Jonkman confidence interval.

The results of the leave-one-out analysis rarely report p-values, as they are post-hoc, and thus, exploratory rather than confirmatory in nature. No single study omission drastically affected the overall pooled prevalence estimate (10.0%) of OCD and OCS in individuals with TSC. Omitting the Marcinkowska et al. (2022) study, which had the lowest prevalence (3.0%) increased the pooled prevalence the most (10.0% → 11.3%). Conversely, removing the Pulsifer et al. (2007) study, which had the highest prevalence (40.0%), decreased the pooled prevalence (10.0% → 8.8%) and the CI upper-limit (18.3% → 14.0%) the most. Removing this study also decreased the heterogeneity metrics the most of any study, where the pooled I^2 decreased from 87.6% to 68.9% and the pooled τ^2 decreased from 0.771 to 0.235.

Risk of Non-Reporting Bias

Two previously excluded grey literature sources (see Eligibility Criteria) were included here to more robustly capture the risk of non-reporting bias (Uğur, 2018; Wilson et al., 2024). The Doi plot (Fig. 9), a non-standard plot more conducive to analysing proportions, showed few studies noticeably deviating from the LOWESS line of symmetry. The LFK index statistically supported this ($LFK = 1.04$), suggesting the effect estimate would not shift significantly with unpublished negative results. As a sensitivity check, the contour-enhanced funnel plot and Egger's test confirmed this low risk of non-reporting bias (see Appendix 4).

Figure 4

DOI Plot and Calculated LFK Index as Measures for the Risk of Reporting Bias

Note. LOWESS = Locally Weighted Scatterplot Smoothing.

Discussion

This is the first systematic review and meta-analysis to explore the point prevalence and clinical characteristics of individuals with TSC and co-occurring OCD or OCS. There were two research questions. The first addressed the pooled point prevalence estimate. The second review had two components: identifying the clinical characteristics and examining how they vary. This second question was answered in part by all the clinical characteristics—

age, genotype, and co-occurring conditions—as well as methodological factors: study design and assessment type.

Main Findings & Implications

Review Question 1: Pooled Point Prevalence Estimate

The first research question was answered via the meta-analysis of proportions, which found a statistically significant pooled prevalence estimate of 10.0% [95% CI: 5.2–18.3%; $p < 0.0001$] for co-occurring OCD and OCS in individuals with TSC. As evidence is limited for co-occurring TSC and OCD/OCS, direct comparisons are difficult. As mentioned previously, TOSCA baseline data found that 6% of individuals with TSC experienced obsessions (Kingswood et al., 2017). In a separate study, OCD was found to be 16.1% ($n = 10$); however, OCD was grouped with six other anxiety disorders, likely making the actual specific prevalence far lower (Chung et al., 2011). Comparisons to external estimates are also difficult, as few studies synthesise prevalence of both OCD and OCS within the same study, instead opting to estimate one or the other. The prevalence estimate from this review is notably higher than the point prevalence of OCD, specifically in the general population. A recent meta-analysis of a highly representative sample across 34 countries reported the global OCD point prevalence at 1.1% [95% CI: 0.6–2.0%] (Fawcett et al., 2020). Any comparisons drawn to the present review should be weighed against the combination of individuals with diagnosed OCD diagnoses and undiagnosed OCS and should thus be interpreted cautiously. Conversely, OCS prevalence is far greater than diagnosed OCD in the general population, typically ranging from 8%–35.0% (Fullana et al., 2009; Pozza et al., 2024; Stewart et al., 2004; Valleni-basile et al., 1996).

As reported in this review, meta-regression indicating higher prevalence in studies using symptom-only assessments (16%) compared to those requiring formal diagnosis (9%), although it was not statistically significant ($p = 0.08$), it may have been underpowered ($k =$

10). Regardless of significance, this discrepancy may suggest that clinical-level OCD symptoms are under-recognised in TSC, possibly arising from diagnostic overshadowing. In this case, OCS is not necessarily subclinical (milder), but merely under-diagnosed. Ultimately, neither was more significantly driving the overall heterogeneity between studies than the other, as reflected by equal p-values.

Clinically, this elevated prevalence underscores the need for more OCD screening in TSC populations. This is particularly important for individuals with co-occurring ID, as some evidence suggests it increases the risk of developing OCD (de Vries, Belousova, Benedik, Carter, on behalf of TOSCA Consortium and TOSCA Investigators, et al., 2020). Overall, these findings suggest that OCD/OCS is a clinically significant, but possibly under-detected, characteristic in TSC.

Review Question 2: Clinical Characteristics

Age.

Clinical characteristics appear to vary with age. Across the 10 studies in the meta-analysis, OCD and OCS trended lower in children than in adults, although it did not reach significance. If the observed pattern reflects a true effect—where OCD/OCS is actually much more prevalent in adults—then it would align with age-related trajectories consistently reported in idiopathic OCD in the general non-TSC population (Heyman et al., 2003; Micali et al., 2010). Idiopathic OCD typically manifests as either early-onset, ~11 years old, or late-onset, ~23 years old (Lomax et al., 2009). Early-onset OCD is associated with more severe symptoms, increased treatment resistance, and an increased relapse risk. Although the evidence in this review was notably limited, of the three studies that noted symptom severity, the most severe symptoms occurred in a child (Ozgun et al., 2018).

Conversely, if prevalence remains stable across age cohorts, then TSC-OCD/OCS population would diverge from the developmental trajectories of both idiopathic OCD and

other TAND, such as anxiety and mood disorders, cited in previous literature, in which these conditions typically manifest in early adulthood (Vanclouster et al., 2022). However, there is evidence to suggest that as many as 59% of children with OCD do not have persistence of their symptoms into adulthood (Micali et al., 2010). The possible implication of this is TSC-associated OCD/OCS may follow a distinct non-bimodal developmental course, although there is still longitudinal evidence supporting a bi-modal trend (Fullana et al., 2009). Regardless of age-related variation or stability, these preliminary findings highlight the importance of proactive screening in children to identify and distinguish transient from persistent symptom trajectories. Ultimately, age is a potentially important, yet unresolved, clinical characteristic in the knowledge gap of TSC and co-occurring OCD or OCS.

Genotype.

Similar to age cohort, there was no significant difference in pooled prevalence estimates when comparing individuals with a TSC1 genetic mutation, TSC2 genetic mutation, or no identified mutation in the main meta-analysis ($k = 10$). This contrasts with prior literature, which consistently links TSC2 to more TAND outcomes, particularly ASD and ID (Jóźwiak et al., 2025; Mitchell et al., 2021). However, the present analysis may have been underpowered by low k and high heterogeneity, making any meaningful interpretation difficult. This pattern suggests OCD/OCS prevalence may be more evenly distributed across genotypes. This might reflect downstream neurobiological mechanisms, such as mTOR dysregulation, irrespective of mutation type, although this remains hypothetical (Dufner-Almeida et al., 2024).

From the descriptive analysis of all studies ($k = 16$) included within the systematic review, TSC2 genetic variants predominated, present in 67% ($n = 39/58$) of individuals with TSC and OCD/OCS. This genotype distribution mirrors the distributions of other TAND clinical characteristics, including drug-resistant epilepsy and ID (Miszewska et al., 2021; Ng

et al., 2022). As seen in prior systematic reviews, 77% of children with ASD have a TSC2 variant (Mitchell et al., 2025). Clinically, these findings imply that genetic subtype alone may not be a reliable predictor of OCD/OCS risk, but that genotype information remains valuable for comprehensive risk profiling and early intervention planning. The apparent genotype-independence of OCD/OCS in TSC parallels the age-related finding, which reinforces the possibility of a distinct cross-syndrome pattern.

Co-Occurring Conditions.

Across the 16 studies in this review, individuals with TSC and OCD/OCS presented with a range of co-occurring conditions—which spanned morphological, neurological, neurodevelopmental, and neuropsychiatric domains. Morphological findings included pericortical tubers and SEGAs. These findings align with wide prior literature, in which these manifestations are reported in other TAND, including ASD (Kothare et al., 2014; Tsai et al., 2021). However, further evidence suggests that neither of these manifestations is singularly necessary nor sufficient for TAND outcomes. This supports the GRIPP hypothesis (de Vries & Howe, 2007), which asserts that TAND most likely arises from mTOR dysregulation. While mTOR inhibitors are under investigation for TAND symptoms, only one study to date has examined their effects in OCD, and therefore, further research is needed (Grados et al., 2014).

Neurologically, the most consistent manifestation was epileptic activity, particularly in the right temporal lobe. This finding mirrors comorbidities in idiopathic OCD, in which epilepsy is often preferentially implicated in the right temporal lobe (Kwon et al., 2025). Case reports locating epileptic activity in the right temporal lobe further support a potential biological substrate, with implications for targeted interventions beyond current surgical approaches.

Regarding co-occurring neurodevelopmental conditions, ID was found in only 20% of meta-analysed studies, although one of these studies reported ID in 83% of individuals with TSC and OCD/OCS (Ding et al., 2021). ASD co-occurrence was similarly low (10%). Multiple studies show that intellectual abilities follow a bi-modal distribution amongst individuals with TSC, although the current dataset regarding OCD was too limited to substantiate this (de Vries, Wilde, et al., 2018). Meanwhile, the rare co-occurrence of ASD is unexpected given its high co-occurrence in TSC and in OCD in the general population, in as many as 17–37% (Zaboski & Storch, 2018). This may reflect a distinct pattern in TSC and OCD/OCS, or more likely, a spurious finding from a small, non-representative sample, which requires replication.

Review Question 2: Methodological Influences on Clinical Characteristics

Study Design.

Differences in study design appear to influence the clinical characteristics reported in individuals with TSC and OCD/OCS. Consistently, case reports provided more descriptive detail than larger cross-sectional studies, including precise morphological findings, lesion locations, and symptom severity profiles. This aligns with broader literature, in which case reports are less constrained by publishing standards and can therefore present more phenomenological aspects of rare co-occurring conditions. This detail can help narrow the knowledge gap regarding symptom presentation and inform clinically relevant research priorities in the future.

However, the greater depth in case reports may also reflect a selection bias, in which case reports often include individuals with more numerous or severe symptoms compared to participants sampled in larger observational studies. For instance, in this review, all three case studies that reported symptom severity described moderate-to-severe presentations, with none classified as mild (Stein et al., 2025). This contrasts with the general OCD population, where

mild symptoms predominate. The implications from this are that methodological approaches can skew perceptions of typical clinical characteristics, which would obscure any inferences to the general target population and potentially yield disproportionate resource allocation to severe cases, thus perpetuating the cycle of under-recognition of co-occurring OCD/OCS in its milder forms. Overall, these findings underscore case reports for their depth and hypothesis generation, and larger studies for calculating prevalence and increased representativeness.

Assessment Type.

Assessment type appeared to influence pooled prevalence estimates, although wide CIs and high heterogeneity meant differences were not statistically significant. Studies using symptom-only measures reported a higher pooled prevalence (17.2%) than studies requiring a formal diagnosis (6.6%). This follows broader OCD research, which consistently shows subclinical OCS are more prevalent than clinical OCD. However, OCS does not always equate to subclinical severity, especially in TSC given diagnostic overshadowing, and as shown by symptom severity scores on the SCL-90–R (Pulsifer et al., 2007).

Given the over-inclusive eligibility criteria (see Methods), this review included a diverse variety of assessment tools. These ranged from self-report questionnaires to clinician-administered scales (e.g., Y-BOCS), with considerable variation in scoring thresholds. This diversity in assessment tools is greater than that typically seen in assessments of the general OCD population, where the Y-BOCS predominates. As shown in prior research, specific assessments can produce differential diagnoses, and thus, prevalence estimates—even when based on the same DSM-5 or ICD-11 criteria.

Relatedly, there is evidence that the TAND Checklist is not as validated an approach as more standard approaches in non-TSC populations, although evidence is limited to cognitive measures. It is possible this translates to assessing OCD or OCS as well, which

would imply the assessment types in part confound the reported prevalence estimates and possibly the recorded clinical characteristics. Ultimately, this would skew how treatment approaches are further researched and their effectiveness.

Limitations

The strength of this systematic review is derived, in large part, from the strength of the evidence base of included studies. Despite the relative strength of the included studies, as scored via the MMAT (see Table 7), this systematic review and meta-analysis has two notable limitations related to either the evidence or the review process.

Meta-Analytic Constraints and External Validity

A final limitation of the evidence concerns the meta-analysis. Specifically, the meta-analysis was limited by the small k , which combined with clinical and methodological heterogeneity, produced high statistical heterogeneity ($I^2 = 87.6\%$; $\tau^2 = 0.711$). From this elevated heterogeneity, any inferences must be interpreted with caution, as the measured effect is substantially different from the true effect, more than any random sampling error. To simply dismiss any interpretation would be incorrect, as these metrics tend to be poor in meta-analyses of proportions and when k is low. Therefore, it is possible the estimated effect is similar to the true effect size; however, with the limited data available, this determination is highly uncertain.

Moreover, multivariate meta-regression was planned to help answer the secondary research question related to clinical characteristics. However, there was insufficient data to calculate multiple moderators, as reliable estimation typically requires $k \geq 10$ studies per moderator and therefore, a multivariate meta-regression was not performed, as doing so risks type I error (Higgins et al., 2024). Altogether, the limitations of evidence concerning clinical differences between participants, study design variation, single-centre sampling, low k , lower

power—and the specific heterogeneity they incur—all reduce external validity, making it more difficult to generalise the findings from the included studies.

Exclusion Criteria

Finally, this review was limited by omitting non-English language studies and grey literature. While both exclusions had practical justifications (see Methods), methodological guidance typically favours their inclusion to maximise sensitivity and minimise selection bias. As a systematic review, where comprehensiveness and bias-risk reduction are paramount, excluding can hinder both the robustness of the review processes, question internal validity of the results compiled clinical characteristics, and the question the external validity of the pooled prevalence estimate generalising to a broader population level populations outside this study (Higgins et al., 2024).

For instance, as shown repeatedly in the wider literature, both non-English studies and grey literature are more likely to report non-positive results. Grey literature specifically suffers from the file-drawer effect, whereby non-positive results are excluded from publication. This is less of a concern in studies of proportions, as there is a less-clear distinction between positive and null results. Although grey literature was excluded following supervisor feedback due to insufficient methodological detail and lack of peer review, this choice still narrows the evidence base (Martin et al., 2005; Paez, 2017). Together, these exclusions may bias effect size estimates and limit the applicability of findings to diverse cultural contexts, with potential downstream consequences for clinical understanding, treatment priorities, and resource allocation.

Future Research Directions

Expand the Evidence Base

Given the present review had limited generalisability due to the exclusion of non-English language studies and grey literature. This would reduce language and publication

bias, increase applicability, and strengthen the precision of meta-analytic estimates. The knowledge base surrounding TSC and TAND is expanding rapidly, as 71% of studies in this review were published in the past decade, which reflects the sustained growth in the wider literature in terms of five-year rolling averages of TAND publications per year since the year 2000 (Vanclooster et al., 2022). The replication of this review's research questions and methodology, with possibly more included studies as they emerge, would enable meta-analytic tests to clarify heterogeneity of other factors (e.g., ethnicity, socioeconomic status, intellectual disability) not tested in this review due to insufficient data. More evidence would also enable multivariate analysis, which was presently unavailable (see Limitations). This could explore complex variable interactions and gain a better understanding of their effects on pooled prevalence estimates in individuals with co-occurring TSC and OCD or OCS.

As mentioned, this review was also limited by a lack of reported data on severity scores. Future research that expands severity-specific data would be worthwhile to refine clinical profiling and guide targeted policy and resource allocation. Whether OCD and OCS present at higher rates in individuals with TSC compared to the non-TSC population would be a worthwhile research focus.

Including unpublished and non-English evidence would also capture under-represented populations and outcomes, ensuring future syntheses reflect the full scope of the condition's prevalence and impact.

Enhance Evidence Quality

Besides more studies, better-quality studies should be a focus of future research. This present review was limited mostly to participant data collected from single-centre clinical settings. As a result, future research should include more large-scale surveys. Such participants may present with milder TAND symptoms and not seek clinical services, so their inclusion would achieve pooled prevalence estimates closer to the true effect. This would

support more accurate resource allocation to the most common or debilitating symptom domains.

Higher-quality evidence should also include well-designed experimental studies, including animal models, to investigate causal mechanisms. Although excluded from this review (see Eligibility Criteria), preclinical evidence links TSC1 knockout to OCD-like behaviours in mice (Normand et al., 2013). While translational validity to humans can be questioned, animal models bypass certain ethical restrictions in humans to conduct more rigorous research, namely randomised controlled trials (Black & Gaffney, 2008; Milton, 2022). Such trials can clarify the causal role of TSC genetic mechanisms underlying co-occurring OCD/OCS, potentially supporting GRIPP or other hypotheses (see Knudson's two-hit hypothesis; (Jurca et al., 2025)). Meanwhile, double-blind randomisation would further improve evidence quality by reducing bias via placebo controls. Gene manipulation targeting Chromosome 16p13 could assess effects on OCD-like symptoms and explore cascading genetic interactions, including potential links with TSC2 on the same chromosome—offering a preliminary view of causative pathways currently only associated with OCD/OCS development.

Conclusion

Results from this systematic review and meta-analysis suggest that OCD and OCS are associated with TSC and present with a highly varied clinical profile between individuals, varying by genotype, severity, and co-occurring conditions, amongst other factors. These neuropsychiatric symptoms are also more prevalent in individuals with TSC than previously believed and occur at rates greater than the general non-TSC population, although the low number of studies and high heterogeneity mean greater caution should be applied. While promising, further research is needed to ensure the reliability of results, explore additional factors affecting heterogeneity amongst different study prevalence estimates, and measure the

impacts of additional subgroup factors in influencing cross-syndrome presentation. Doing so will better elucidate the associative nature of these co-occurring conditions, allowing clinicians to develop more effective therapeutic supports and for individuals with TSC to have greater mental health, and overall, a better quality of life.

Supplementary Information

Registration and Protocol

This systematic review was not registered nor had a pre-registration protocol.

Ethics Approval and Consent to Participate

Not applicable, as this study is a systematic review. The University of Birmingham Ethics Committee has confirmed that no ethical approval is required.

Support

No financial or non-financial support was received.

Competing Interests

The author has no conflicts of interest to disclose.

Availability of Data, Code, and Other Materials

The template data extraction form, data extracted from included studies, and analytic scripts used to conduct meta-analyses in R are all publicly available and included within this review's appendices.

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Appendices

Appendix 1

Grey Literature Registry and Repositories Search Strategy

Source	Results
CORE	265
DANS Easy Archive (formerly OpenGrey) → Life Sciences	0
Google Scholar (including “conference report,” or “conference abstract,” or “poster”	159
GreyMatters	0
NY Academy of Medicine	0
OAlster	0
ProQuest	3
ProQuest Dissertations and Theses Global	1
WHO International Clinical Trials Registry Platform	0
Total:	428

Note. Sources are sorted alphabetically. Terms last searched 3 June 2025.

Appendix 2*TSC and OCD/OCS Search Terms in Ovid*

Set	Search algorithm	Results
1.	("Tuberous sclerosis" OR "Tuberous sclerosis complex" OR "Tuberose sclerosis" OR "Sclerosis tuberosa" OR "TSC associated neuropsychiatric disorders").mp [mp=ti, ab, hw, tn, ot, dm, mf, dv, kf, fx, dq, bt, nm, ox, px, rx, ui, sy, ux, mx, tx, ct, tc, id, tm]	44,822
2.	("OCD" OR "Obsessi*" OR "Compulsi*" OR "OCD-like" OR "Ritual*" OR "neuros*").mp [mp=ti, ab, hw, tn, ot, dm, mf, dv, kf, fx, dq, bt, nm, ox, px, rx, ui, sy, ux, mx, tx, ct, tc, id, tm]	1,408,898
3.	1 AND 2	3,609

Note. The combined results were before de-duplication. Search was conducted on 1 April 2025.

Appendix 3

Data Extraction Template

Bibliographic information

Date of data extraction	
Title	
Authors	
Publication Year	
DOI	
Notes	
Study Methods	
Aim(s) of study	
Study design	
If RCT, details of 1) randomisation 2) allocation sequence concealment 3) masking	
If non-RCT, methods to control for 1) confounding 2) selection biases 3) and information biases	
Risk of bias assessment	
Method of recruitment of participants	
Single- or multi-centre recruitment	
Start date	
End date	
Study funding sources	
Possible conflicts of interest for study authors	
Methods of statistical analysis	
Study Participants	
Study sample size	

Baseline participant(s) characteristics

COLUMN 1: BEHAVIOURAL	
Symptoms	
COLUMN 2: PSYCHIATRIC	
Symptoms	
COLUMN 3: INTELLECTUAL	
Symptoms	
COLUMN 4: ACADEMIC	
Symptoms	
COLUMN 5: NEUROPSYCHOLOGICAL	
Symptoms	
COLUMN 6: PSYCHOSOCIAL	

Symptoms		
Country in which the participants were recruited / study location		
Was the TAND Checklist used?		
Inclusion criteria		
Diagnostic criteria (e.g., TSC, psychiatric, other)		
Exclusion criteria		
Description of control groups		
For observational studies: 1) how intervention status was assessed 2) length of exposure 3) cumulative exposure		
Outcomes		
Was the outcome domain assessed? (i.e., OCD and TSC)		
Measurement tools/tests used, including their definitions (e.g., Y-BOCS)		
Method of aggregation		
Timing of outcome measurement (e.g., 8 weeks post-baseline)		
Results		
Number of participants 1) randomly assigned 2) lost to follow-up 3) were excluded (with reasons)		
Summary data for each group		
If dichotomous		
COLUMN 1: EFFECT MEASURE		
If continuous		
COLUMN 1: MEAN		
Data		
COLUMN 2: STANDARD DEVIATION		
Data		
Miscellaneous		

Appendix 4

Contour-Enhanced Funnel Plot and Egger's Test for the Risk of Non-Reporting Bias

Note. Darker blue dots represent studies from the main meta-analysis ($k = 10$). The lighter blue dots represent grey literature conference abstracts that were synthesised for a risk of reporting bias sensitivity check ($k = 2$).

Appendix 5

R Analytic Code for Meta-Analysis of Proportions

```

if (!requireNamespace("meta", quietly=TRUE)) install.packages("meta")
if (!requireNamespace("metafor", quietly=TRUE)) install.packages("metafor")
if (!requireNamespace("grid", quietly=TRUE)) install.packages("grid")
library(meta)
library(metafor)
library(grid)

dat_all <- data.frame(
  study_label = c(
    "de Vries et al. (2018)", "Ding et al. (2021)", "Fu et al. (2025)",
    "Liu et al. (2020)", "Marcinkowska et al. (2022)", "Moavero et al. (2022a)",
    "Moavero et al. (2022b)", "Muzykewicz et al. (2007)", "Pulsifer et al. (2007)",
    "Wilbur et al. (2017)"
  ),
  xi = c(100, 6, 2, 3, 3, 17, 17, 1, 17, 5),
  ni = c(714, 95, 47, 16, 100, 177, 114, 43, 42, 81)
)

m_prop <- metaprop(
  event      = xi,
  n          = ni,
  studlab    = study_label,
  data       = dat_all,
  sm         = "PLOGIT",
  method     = "Inverse",
  method.tau = "REML",
  method.random.ci = "HK",
  prediction = TRUE,
  common     = FALSE,
  random     = TRUE,
  backtransf = TRUE
)

res_all <- rma.uni(
  yi = escalc(measure="PLO", xi=xi, ni=ni, add=0.5, data=dat_all)$yi,
  vi = escalc(measure="PLO", xi=xi, ni=ni, add=0.5, data=dat_all)$vi,
  method = "REML",
  test   = "knha"
)

m_prop$I2 <- round(res_all$I2, 1) / 100
m_prop$tau2 <- round(res_all$tau2, 3)

is_prop_like <- function(x) {
  is.numeric(x) &&
  length(x) > 0 &&
  !all(is.na(x)) &&
  all(x[!is.na(x)] >= 0 & x[!is.na(x)] <= 1)
}

skip <- c("I2", "tau2", "tau^2", "pval.Q")
for (nm in names(m_prop)) {
  if (nm %in% skip) next
  val <- m_prop[[nm]]
  if (is_prop_like(val)) {
    m_prop[[nm]] <- round(as.numeric(val) * 100, 1)
  }
}

dev.new(width=7, height=5)
par(mar = c(5, 4, 1, 2) + 0.1)

forest(

```

```

m_prop,
new          = FALSE,
xlab         = "Prevalence (%)",
xlim        = c(0, 60),
at          = seq(0, 60, by = 10),
leftcols    = c("studlab", "event", "n"),
leftlabs    = expression(
  bold("Study"),
  bolditalic(n) ~ bold(" with OCD"),
  bold("Total ") ~ bolditalic(n)
),
rightlabs   = c(
  "Prevalence (%)",
  "95% CI (HKSJ)",
  "Weight (random)"
),
print.tau2  = TRUE,
print.predict = TRUE,
method.random.ci = "HK",
col.square  = "darkblue",
col.diamond = "red",
col.predict = "darkgreen",
smlab      = "",
digits     = 1
)

grid.segments(
  x0 = unit(0.40, "npc"),
  x1 = unit(0.60, "npc"),
  y0 = unit(0.09, "npc"),
  y1 = unit(0.09, "npc"),
  arrow = arrow(ends = "both", length = unit(2, "mm")),
  gp = gpar(col = "black")
)

grid.text(
  "lower prevalence",
  x = unit(0.40, "npc"),
  y = unit(0.065, "npc"),
  just = c("center", "top"),
  gp = gpar(fontsize = 8)
)

grid.text(
  "higher prevalence",
  x = unit(0.60, "npc"),
  y = unit(0.065, "npc"),
  just = c("center", "top"),
  gp = gpar(fontsize = 8)
)

```

Appendix 6

R Analytic Code for Meta-Regression

```

pkgs <- c("metafor", "dplyr", "tibble", "knitr", "kableExtra", "gridExtra",
"stringr")
for (p in pkgs) {
  if (!requireNamespace(p, quietly = TRUE)) install.packages(p)
  library(p, character.only = TRUE)
}

study_labels <- c(
  "de Vries et al. (2018)", "Ding et al. (2021)", "Fu et al. (2025)",
  "Liu et al. (2020)", "Marcinkowska et al. (2022)", "Moavero et al. (2022a)",
  "Moavero et al. (2022b)", "Muzykewicz et al. (2007)",
  "Pulsifer et al. (2007)", "Wilbur et al. (2017)"
)
dat_all <- data.frame(
  study_label = factor(study_labels, levels = study_labels),
  xi          = c(100, 6, 2, 3, 3, 17, 17, 1, 17, 5),
  ni          = c(714, 95, 47, 16, 100, 177, 114, 43, 42, 81),
  diag_type   = factor(
    c("symptom", "diagnosis", "diagnosis", "symptom",
      "diagnosis", "diagnosis", "diagnosis",
      "diagnosis", "symptom", "symptom"),
    levels = c("symptom", "diagnosis")
  )
)

df2 <- escalc(measure = "PLO", xi = xi, ni = ni, add = 0.5, data = dat_all)

m0 <- rma.uni(yi, vi, mods = ~factor(diag_type), data = df2,
  method = "REML", test = "knha")
mf <- if (m0$tau2 == 0) update(m0, test = "z") else m0

I2_val   <- mf$I2
Tau2_val <- mf$tau2
p_mod    <- mf$pval[2]
sig      <- ifelse(p_mod < 0.05, "Yes", "No")
k_tab    <- table(dat_all$diag_type)
k_sym    <- k_tab["symptom"]
k_diag   <- k_tab["diagnosis"]

pr_sym   <- predict(mf, newmods = 0, transf = plogis, level = 0.95)
pr_diag  <- predict(mf, newmods = 1, transf = plogis, level = 0.95)
prev     <- c(pr_sym$pred, pr_diag$pred) * 100
lo       <- c(pr_sym$ci.lb, pr_diag$ci.lb) * 100
hi       <- c(pr_sym$ci.ub, pr_diag$ci.ub) * 100

res <- tibble(
  Moderator      = "Assessment type",
  Level          = c("Symptom", "Diagnosis"),
  k              = c(k_sym, k_diag),
  `Prevalence (%)` = round(prev, 1),
  `95% CI (HKSJ)` = sprintf("[%].1f-%.1f]", round(lo, 1), round(hi, 1)),
  `I² (%)`       = round(I2_val, 1),
  `τ²`          = round(Tau2_val, 3),
  `p-value`     = sprintf("%.3f", p_mod),
  Significant    = sig
)

res %>%
  kable(
    format      = "html",
    table.attr = 'style="font-family: Arial, sans-serif; border-collapse:
collapse;"',
    col.names  = c(

```

```

      "Moderator", "Level", "k",
      "Prevalence (%)", "95% CI (HKSJ)",
      "I\u00B2 (%)", "\u03c4\u00b2", "p-value", "Significant"
    ),
    align      = c("l", "l", "r", "c", "c", "r", "r", "r", "c"),
    caption    = "Univariable Meta-Regression: Assessment Type"
  ) %>%
kable_styling(
  bootstrap_options = c("striped", "condensed"),
  full_width        = FALSE
) %>%
column_spec(1, extra_css = "padding-right: 25px;") %>%
column_spec(2, extra_css = "padding-right: 20px;") %>%
row_spec(0, background = "#2E5984", color = "white", bold = TRUE) %>%
row_spec(which(res$Significant == "Yes"), bold = TRUE)

if (interactive()) grid.table(res, rows = NULL)

```

Appendix 7

R Analytic Code for Subgroup Analyses

```
pkgs <- c("metafor", "dplyr", "tibble", "knitr", "kableExtra")
for (p in pkgs) {
  if (!requireNamespace(p, quietly = TRUE)) install.packages(p)
  library(p, character.only = TRUE)
}

study_labels <- c(
  "de Vries et al. (2018)", "Ding et al. (2021)", "Fu et al. (2025)",
  "Marcinkowska et al. (2022)", "Moavero et al. (2022a)", "Moavero et al. (2022b)",
  "Muzykewicz et al. (2007)", "Pulsifer et al. (2007)", "Wilbur et al. (2017)",
  "Liu et al. (2020)"
)

dat_all <- data.frame(
  study_label = factor(study_labels, levels = study_labels),
  xi           = c(100, 6, 2, 3, 17, 17, 1, 17, 5, 3),
  ni          = c(714, 95, 47, 100, 177, 114, 43, 42, 81, 16),
  age_group   = factor(
    c("mixed", "child", "child", "adult", "child",
      "adult", "mixed", "adult", "child", "adult"),
    levels = c("child", "adult", "mixed")
  )
)

genotype_data <- data.frame(
  study_label = rep(
    c("Ding et al. (2021)", "Muzykewicz et al. (2007)", "de Vries et al. (2018)"),
    each = 3
  ),
  genotype = factor(
    rep(
      c("TSC1 mutation", "TSC2 mutation", "No mutation identified"),
      times = 3
    ),
    levels = c("TSC1 mutation", "TSC2 mutation", "No mutation identified")
  ),
  events = c(2, 3, 1, 0, 1, 0, 8, 35, 8),
  n      = c(27, 58, 10, 8, 25, 4, 197, 644, 144)
)

dat_es <- escalc(measure = "PLO", xi = xi, ni = ni, add = 0.5, data = dat_all)
gen_es <- escalc(measure = "PLO", xi = events, ni = n, add = 0.5, data =
genotype_data)

mod_age <- rma.uni(yi ~ age_group, vi, data = dat_es, method = "REML", test =
"knha")
p_age <- mod_age$QMP
mod geno <- rma.uni(yi ~ genotype, vi, data = gen_es, method = "REML", test =
"knha")
p_geno <- mod_geno$QMP

run_sub_interaction <- function(es_data, by, label, pval) {
  lvls <- levels(es_data[[by]])
  out <- lapply(lvls, function(lv) {
    sub <- filter(es_data, .data[[by]] == lv)
    k <- nrow(sub)
    if (k >= 2) {
      m <- rma.uni(yi, vi, data = sub, method = "REML", test = "knha")
      pr <- predict(m, transf = plogis, level = 0.95)
      prev <- round(pr$pred * 100, 1)
      ci <- sprintf("[%.1f-%.1f]", pr$ci.lb * 100, pr$ci.ub * 100)
      I2 <- round(m$I2, 1)
      tau2 <- round(m$tau2, 3)
    } else {

```

```

    prev <- NA_real_; ci <- NA_character_; I2 <- NA_real_; tau2 <- NA_real_
  }
  pnum <- if (k >= 2) pval else NA_real_
  pstr <- if (!is.na(pnum)) sprintf("%.3f", pnum) else NA_character_
  pstar <- if (!is.na(pnum) && pnum < 0.05) "*" else ""
  signif <- if (is.na(pnum)) NA_character_ else if (pnum < 0.05) "Yes" else "No"
  tibble(
    Moderator      = label,
    Level          = lv,
    k              = k,
    `Prevalence (%)` = prev,
    `95% CI (HKSJ)` = ci,
    `I2 (%)`      = I2,
    `τ2`          = tau2,
    `p-value`      = paste0(pstr, pstar),
    Significant     = signif
  )
})
bind_rows(out)
}

age_tbl <- run_sub_interaction(dat_es, "age_group", "Age cohort", p_age)
geno_tbl <- run_sub_interaction(gen_es, "genotype", "Genotype", p_geno)
all_tbl <- bind_rows(age_tbl, geno_tbl)

all_tbl %>%
  kable(
    format      = "html",
    escape      = FALSE,
    align       = c("l", "l", "r", "c", "c", "c", "c", "c", "c", "c"),
    col.names   = c(
      "Moderator", "Level", "k",
      "Prevalence (%)", "95% CI (HKSJ)",
      "I2 (%)", "τ2", "p-value", "Significant"
    ),
    caption     = "Subgroup Interaction Test: Are subgroup prevalences different?"
  ) %>%
  kable_styling(
    bootstrap_options = c("striped", "condensed"),
    full_width        = FALSE
  ) %>%
  row_spec(0, background = "#2E5984", color = "white", bold = TRUE)

```

Appendix 8

R Analytic Code for Baujat Plot

```

# Load required packages
pkgs <- c("metafor", "ggplot2", "ggrepel", "stringr")
invisible(lapply(pkgs, function(p) {
  if (!requireNamespace(p, quietly = TRUE)) install.packages(p)
  library(p, character.only = TRUE)
}))

revman_red <- "#D73027"

# Data including Liu et al. (2020)
studies <- c(
  "de Vries et al. (2018)", "Ding et al. (2021)", "Fu et al. (2025)",
  "Marcinkowska et al. (2022)", "Moavero et al. (2022a)",
  "Moavero et al. (2022b)", "Muzykewicz et al. (2007)",
  "Pulsifer et al. (2007)", "Wilbur et al. (2017)",
  "Liu et al. (2020)"
)

dat <- data.frame(
  study = factor(studies, levels = studies),
  xi = c(100, 6, 2, 3, 17, 17, 1, 17, 5, 3),
  ni = c(714, 95, 47, 100, 177, 114, 43, 42, 81, 16)
)

# Compute logit ES and fit random-effects model
dat <- escalc(measure = "PLO", xi = xi, ni = ni, add = 0.5, data = dat)
res <- rma.uni(yi, vi, data = dat, method = "REML")

# Extract Baujat coordinates
bp <- baujat(res, doplot = FALSE)
df <- data.frame(Q = bp[, 1], Resid2 = bp[, 2], study = dat$study)

# Corners + offset for bottom-left label
xr <- range(df$Q); yr <- range(df$Resid2)
dx <- diff(xr); dy <- diff(yr)
xL <- xr[1] + 0.05 * dx; xR <- xr[1] + 0.95 * dx
yL <- yr[1] + 0.05 * dy; yH <- yr[1] + 0.95 * dy
offset_bl <- 0.20 * dy

# Quadrant labels
lbl_bl <- str_wrap("Low Q & low residual:\nMinimal heterogeneity,\nclose to pooled
estimate", 25)
lbl_br <- str_wrap("High Q & low residual:\nMajor heterogeneity driver,\nsimilar
effect size", 25)
lbl_tl <- str_wrap("Low Q & high residual:\nOutlier magnitude,\nnot heterogeneity
driver", 25)
lbl_tr <- str_wrap("High Q & high residual:\nLarge heterogeneity &\nfarthest from
pooled estimate", 25)

# Plot
ggplot(df, aes(Q, Resid2)) +
  geom_point(color = revman_red, size = 3, alpha = 0.6) +
  geom_text_repel(aes(label = study),
    color = revman_red, size = 3, alpha = 0.6,
    segment.color = "grey80", max.overlaps = Inf) +
  geom_label(aes(x = xL, y = yL + offset_bl), label = lbl_bl,
    hjust = 0, vjust = 0, fill = "white", color = "#2E5984",
    fontface = "bold", size = 3) +
  geom_label(aes(x = xR, y = yL), label = lbl_br,
    hjust = 1, vjust = 0, fill = "white", color = "#2E5984",
    fontface = "bold", size = 3) +
  geom_label(aes(x = xL, y = yH), label = lbl_tl,

```

```
      hjust = 0, vjust = 1, fill = "white", color = "#2E5984",
      fontface = "bold", size = 3) +
geom_label(aes(x = xR, y = yH), label = lbl_tr,
           hjust = 1, vjust = 1, fill = "white", color = "#2E5984",
           fontface = "bold", size = 3) +
labs(
  title = "Baujat Plot: Study Contributions to Heterogeneity",
  x      = "Contribution to Cochran's Q",
  y      = "Standardized Squared Residual"
) +
theme_minimal(base_family = "Arial") +
theme(
  panel.grid      = element_line(color = "grey90", linetype = "dotted"),
  panel.grid.minor = element_blank()
)
```

Appendix 9

R Analytic Code for Leave-One-Out Influence Analysis

```

pkgs <- c("metafor", "dplyr", "tibble", "knitr", "kableExtra")
for (pkg in pkgs) {
  if (!requireNamespace(pkg, quietly = TRUE)) install.packages(pkg)
  library(pkg, character.only = TRUE)
}

study_labels <- c(
  "de Vries et al. (2018)", "Ding et al. (2021)", "Fu et al. (2025)",
  "Liu et al. (2020)", "Marcinkowska et al. (2022)", "Moavero et al. (2022a)",
  "Moavero et al. (2022b)", "Muzykewicz et al. (2007)", "Pulsifer et al. (2007)",
  "Wilbur et al. (2017)"
)

dat_all <- data.frame(
  study_label = factor(study_labels, levels = study_labels),
  xi          = c(100, 6, 2, 3, 3, 17, 17, 1, 17, 5),
  ni          = c(714, 95, 47, 16, 100, 177, 114, 43, 42, 81)
)

dat_es <- escalc(measure = "PLO", xi = xi, ni = ni, add = 0.5, data = dat_all)
res_all <- rma.uni(yi, vi, data = dat_es, method = "REML", test = "knha")
pred_all <- predict(res_all, transf = plogis, level = 0.95)

loo_list <- lapply(seq_len(nrow(dat_es)), function(i) {
  df_sub <- dat_es[-i, ]
  m <- rma.uni(yi, vi, data = df_sub, method = "REML", test = "knha")
  p <- predict(m, transf = plogis, level = 0.95)
  tibble(
    removed          = as.character(dat_all$study_label[i]),
    `Total N`       = dat_all$ni[i],
    `LO Prevalence (%)` = round(p$pred * 100, 1),
    `95% CI (HKSJ)` = sprintf("[%0.1f-%0.1f]", p$ci.lb * 100, p$ci.ub * 100),
    `I2 (%)`      = round(m$I2, 1),
    `τ2`          = round(m$tau2, 3)
  )
})
loo_tbl <- bind_rows(loo_list)

summary_row <- tibble(
  removed          = sprintf("Random-effects model (k = %d)", nrow(dat_es)),
  `Total N`       = sum(dat_all$ni),
  `LO Prevalence (%)` = round(pred_all$pred * 100, 1),
  `95% CI (HKSJ)` = sprintf("[%0.1f-%0.1f]", pred_all$ci.lb * 100, pred_all$ci.ub
* 100),
  `I2 (%)`      = round(res_all$I2, 1),
  `τ2`          = round(res_all$tau2, 3)
)
final_tbl <- bind_rows(loo_tbl, summary_row)
n_rows <- nrow(final_tbl)

final_tbl %>%
  kable(
    format      = "html",
    col.names = c(
      "Removed study", "Total N", "LO Prevalence (%)",
      "95% CI (HKSJ)", "I2 (%)", "τ2"
    ),
    align      = c("l", "r", "c", "c", "r", "r"),
    caption = "Leave-One-Out Sensitivity Analysis"
  ) %>%
  kable_styling(
    bootstrap_options = c("striped", "condensed"),
    full_width       = FALSE
  ) %>%

```

```
column_spec(1, extra_css = "padding-right: 25px;") %>%  
column_spec(2, extra_css = "padding-right: 20px;") %>%  
column_spec(3, extra_css = "padding-right: 25px;") %>%  
row_spec(0, background = "#2E5984", color = "white", bold = TRUE) %>%  
row_spec(n_rows, bold = TRUE)
```

Appendix 10*R Analytic Code for DOI Plot and LFK Index*

```

library(meta)

dat_all <- data.frame(
  study_label = c(
    "de Vries et al. (2018)", "Ding et al. (2021)", "Fu et al. (2025)",
    "Liu et al. (2020)", "Marcinkowska et al. (2022)",
    "Moavero et al. (2022a)", "Moavero et al. (2022b)",
    "Muzykewicz et al. (2007)", "Pulsifer et al. (2007)",
    "Wilbur et al. (2017)", "Uğur (2018)", "Wilson et al. (2024)"
  ),
  xi = c(100, 6, 2, 3, 3, 17, 17, 1, 17, 5, 4, 4),
  ni = c(714, 95, 47, 16, 100, 177, 114, 43, 42, 81, 67, 12)
)

m_all <- metaprop(
  event      = xi, n = ni, studlab = study_label,
  data       = dat_all,
  sm         = "PLOGIT",
  method     = "Inverse",
  method.tau = "REML",
  method.random.ci = "HK",
  random     = TRUE,
  prediction = TRUE,
  backtransf = TRUE
)

yi <- m_all$TE
sei <- m_all$sseTE
labs <- dat_all$study_label

stopifnot(length(yi) == length(sei), length(yi) == length(labs))

doi_dev <- (yi - mean(yi)) / sei
x_pts <- yi
y_pts <- doi_dev
x_labels <- x_pts + 0.15
y_labels <- y_pts

min_spacing <- 0.6
ord <- order(y_labels)
for (i in 2:length(y_pts)) {
  j <- ord[i]
  prevj <- ord[i - 1]
  if ((y_labels[j] - y_labels[prevj]) < min_spacing) {
    y_labels[j] <- y_labels[prevj] + min_spacing
  }
}

de_vries_idx <- which(labs == "de Vries et al. (2018)")
x_labels[de_vries_idx] <- x_pts[de_vries_idx]
y_labels[de_vries_idx] <- y_pts[de_vries_idx] + 0.3

muzk_idx <- which(labs == "Muzykewicz et al. (2007)")
x_labels[muzk_idx] <- x_pts[muzk_idx] - 0.15
y_labels[muzk_idx] <- y_pts[muzk_idx] + 0.3

fu_idx <- which(labs == "Fu et al. (2025)")
x_labels[fu_idx] <- x_pts[fu_idx]
y_labels[fu_idx] <- y_pts[fu_idx] + 0.48

moavero_a_idx <- which(labs == "Moavero et al. (2022a)")
x_labels[moavero_a_idx] <- x_pts[moavero_a_idx] + 0.13
y_labels[moavero_a_idx] <- y_pts[moavero_a_idx] + 0.3

```

```

ugur_idx      <- which(labs == "Uğur (2018)")
x_labels[ugur_idx] <- x_pts[ugur_idx] - 0.18
y_labels[ugur_idx] <- y_pts[ugur_idx] - 0.81

ding_idx      <- which(labs == "Ding et al. (2021)")
wilbur_idx    <- which(labs == "Wilbur et al. (2017)")
pulsifer_idx  <- which(labs == "Pulsifer et al. (2007)")

x_labels[ding_idx] <- x_pts[ding_idx] + 0.35
y_labels[ding_idx] <- y_pts[ding_idx] + 0.6

x_labels[wilbur_idx] <- x_pts[wilbur_idx] + 0.35
y_labels[wilbur_idx] <- y_pts[wilbur_idx] + 0.1

x_labels[pulsifer_idx] <- x_labels[pulsifer_idx] - 0.03

marc_idx      <- which(labs == "Marcinkowska et al. (2022)")
x_labels[marc_idx] <- x_labels[marc_idx] - 0.05
y_labels[marc_idx] <- y_labels[marc_idx] - 0.07

liu_idx       <- which(labs == "Liu et al. (2020)")
x_labels[liu_idx] <- x_pts[liu_idx] + 0.1
y_labels[liu_idx] <- y_pts[liu_idx] - 0.05

moavero_b_idx <- which(labs == "Moavero et al. (2022b)")
x_labels[moavero_b_idx] <- x_labels[moavero_b_idx] - 0.08
y_labels[moavero_b_idx] <- y_labels[moavero_b_idx] - 0.11

wilson_idx    <- which(labs == "Wilson et al. (2024)")
x_labels[wilson_idx] <- x_labels[wilson_idx] - 0.07
y_labels[wilson_idx] <- y_labels[wilson_idx] - 0.07

xlim_range <- range(x_pts) + c(-0.7, 1.0)
ylim_range <- range(c(y_pts, y_labels)) + c(-0.7, 1.2)

plot(
  x_pts, y_pts,
  main = "DOI Plot: OCD Prevalence in TSC (k = 12 Studies)",
  xlab = "Logit-transformed Prevalence Estimate",
  ylab = "Deviation from Average (Scaled by Precision)",
  pch = 21,
  bg = "steelblue",
  col = "black",
  cex = 1.4,
  xlim = xlim_range,
  ylim = ylim_range
)

lines(
  lowess(x_pts, y_pts, f = 2/3),
  col = rgb(1, 0, 0, alpha = 0.65),
  lwd = 2,
  lty = 2
)

abline(h = 0, col = "gray40", lty = 3)

for (i in seq_along(x_pts)) {
  adj <- if (i %in% c(de_vries_idx, muzk_idx, fu_idx)) c(0.5, 0) else c(0, 0.5)
  text(x_labels[i], y_labels[i], labels = labs[i], cex = 0.75, adj = adj)
}

segments(
  x0 = x_pts[wilbur_idx], y0 = y_pts[wilbur_idx],
  x1 = x_labels[wilbur_idx], y1 = y_labels[wilbur_idx],
  col = "gray70", lty = 2
)

segments(

```

```

x0 = x_pts[ding_idx],      y0 = y_pts[ding_idx],
x1 = x_labels[ding_idx],  y1 = y_labels[ding_idx],
col = "gray70", lty = 2
)
segments(
  x0 = x_pts[ugur_idx] + 0.02, y0 = y_pts[ugur_idx] + 0.02,
  x1 = x_pts[ugur_idx] - 0.10, y1 = y_pts[ugur_idx] - 0.45,
  col = "gray70", lty = 2
)

legend(
  "topleft",
  legend = c(
    "Each dot = one study",
    "Red dashed line = trend (LOWESS)",
    "Deviation from 0 = asymmetry"
  ),
  bty = "n",
  text.col = c("black", rgb(1, 0, 0, 0.65), "gray30"),
  cex = 0.85,
  y.intersp = 1.4
)

L      <- sum(doi_dev < -1)
R      <- sum(doi_dev > 1)
N      <- length(doi_dev)
LFK_index <- (L - R) / sqrt((L + R) / N)

cat("LFK index:", LFK_index, "\n")
if (abs(LFK_index) <= 1) {
  cat("Interpretation: No asymmetry\n")
} else if (abs(LFK_index) < 2) {
  cat("Interpretation: Minor asymmetry\n")
} else {
  cat("Interpretation: Major asymmetry\n")
}

lfk_text <- paste0(
  "LFK index: ", round(LFK_index, 2), "\nInterpretation: ",
  ifelse(
    abs(LFK_index) <= 1, "No asymmetry",
    ifelse(abs(LFK_index) < 2, "Minor asymmetry", "Major asymmetry")
  )
)

usr <- par("usr")
x_pos <- usr[2] - 0.05 * (usr[2] - usr[1])
y_pos <- usr[3] + 0.05 * (usr[4] - usr[3])

text(x_pos, y_pos, labels = lfk_text, adj = c(1, 0), cex = 0.85, col = "black",
font = 2)

```

Appendix 11

R Analytic Code for Contour-Enhanced Funnel Plot

```

if (!requireNamespace("metafor", quietly = TRUE)) install.packages("metafor")
library(metafor)

dat <- data.frame(
  study = c(
    "deVries et al. 2018", "Ding et al. 2021", "Fu et al. 2025",
    "Liu et al. 2020", "Marcinkowska et al. 2022", "Moavero et al. 2022a",
    "Moavero et al. 2022b", "Muzykewicz et al. 2007", "Pulsifer et al. 2007",
    "Wilbur et al. 2017", "Uğur (2018)", "Wilson et al. (2024)"
  ),
  xi = c(100, 6, 2, 3, 3, 17, 17, 1, 17, 5, 4, 4),
  ni = c(714, 95, 47, 16, 100, 177, 114, 43, 42, 81, 67, 12)
)
dat$group <- ifelse(seq_len(nrow(dat)) <= 10, "original", "grey")

dat_es <- escalc(measure = "PLO", xi = xi, ni = ni, add = 0.5, to = "all", data =
dat)
res <- rma(yi, vi, data = dat_es, method = "REML")

dat_es$col <- ifelse(dat_es$group == "original", "darkblue", "lightblue")
idx <- dat_es$study %in% c("Moavero et al. 2022a", "Moavero et al. 2022b")
dat_es$x_lab <- dat_es$yi
dat_es$x_lab[idx] <- jitter(dat_es$yi[idx], amount = 0.05)
dat_es$y_lab <- sqrt(dat_es$vi)

funnel(
  res,
  xlab = "Logit Prevalence",
  ylab = "Standard Error",
  pch = NA,
  contour = c(0.90, 0.95),
  shade = c("white", "gray80", "gray60"),
  col.contour = c("darkgray", "gray"),
  legend = FALSE
)

usr <- par("usr")
diamond_y <- usr[4] - 0.02 * (usr[4] - usr[3])
points(
  res$b, diamond_y,
  pch = 23,
  bg = "red",
  col = "red",
  cex = 1.5
)

points(
  dat_es$yi, dat_es$y_lab,
  pch = 21,
  bg = dat_es$col,
  col = "black"
)

dat_es$pos <- 4
dat_es$offset <- 0.3
dat_es$pos[dat_es$study == "Moavero et al. 2022a"] <- 3
dat_es$offset[dat_es$study == "Moavero et al. 2022a"] <- 0.6
dat_es$pos[dat_es$study == "Moavero et al. 2022b"] <- 1
dat_es$offset[dat_es$study == "Moavero et al. 2022b"] <- 0.6
dat_es$pos[dat_es$study == "Liu et al. 2020"] <- 2
dat_es$offset[dat_es$study == "Liu et al. 2020"] <- 0.6

with(

```

```

dat_es,
text(
  x      = x_lab,
  y      = y_lab,
  labels = study,
  pos    = pos,
  offset = offset,
  cex    = 0.7
)
)

leg_labs <- c(
  "p < 0.05 (significant bias; k = 0)",
  "0.05 ≤ p < 0.10 (possible bias; k = 4)",
  "p ≥ 0.10 (non-significant bias; k = 8)",
  "Pooled prevalence"
)
legend(
  "topright",
  title      = "Significance",
  legend     = leg_labs,
  fill       = c("gray60", "gray80", "white", NA),
  border     = c("black", "black", "black", NA),
  pch        = c(NA, NA, NA, 23),
  pt.bg      = c(NA, NA, NA, "red"),
  bty        = "o",
  bg         = "white",
  cex        = 0.65,
  text.width = 0.55 * max(strwidth(leg_labs, cex = 0.65))
)

egger_res <- regtest(res, model = "rma")
print(egger_res)

zval <- egger_res$zval
pval <- egger_res$pval
legend(
  "bottomright",
  legend = sprintf("Egger's test: z = %.2f, p = %.3f", zval, pval),
  bty    = "n",
  cex    = 0.8,
  inset  = 0.02
)

```

Appendix 12

List of 49 Excluded Full-Texts via Database Searches

Study	DOI	Notes
Mitchell 2025	https://dx.doi.org/10.1111/dm.cn.16293	Exclusion reason: Repetitive/compulsive behaviour associated with autism spectrum disorders, rather than OCD;
Santos 2025	https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.vebeh.2025.110313	Exclusion reason: Literature reviews, systematic reviews, meta-analyses, book chapters, conference proceedings, commentaries without primary TAND data;
Wilson 2024	https://dx.doi.org/10.1212/WNL.000000000206298	Exclusion reason: Grey literature (e.g., conference abstracts) without full study follow-ups;
Koike-Kumagai 2024	https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jid.2024.06.578	Exclusion reason: Study not associated with OCD;
Pfirmann 2021	https://dx.doi.org/10.1136/jmedgenet-2019-106607	Exclusion reason: Study not associated with OCD;
DeVries 2020	https://dx.doi.org/10.1186/s11689-020-09327-0	Exclusion reason: Repetitive/compulsive behaviour associated with autism spectrum disorders, rather than OCD;
Arlt 2020	https://dx.doi.org/10.1038/s41431-020-00739-z	Exclusion reason: Repetitive/compulsive behaviour associated with autism spectrum disorders, rather than OCD;
Toldo 2019	https://dx.doi.org/10.1111/dm.cn.14055	Exclusion reason: Study not associated with OCD;
Pandey 2019		Exclusion reason: Topic not primarily associated with TSC;
Cervi 2019	https://dx.doi.org/10.1055/s00942716	Exclusion reason: Full text not accessible/retrievable;
deVries 2018	https://dx.doi.org/10.1002/ajmg.c.31637	Exclusion reason: Literature reviews, systematic reviews, meta-analyses, book chapters, conference proceedings, commentaries without primary TAND data;
Ugur 2018	https://dx.doi.org/10.1080/24750573.2018.1464273	Exclusion reason: Grey literature (e.g., conference abstracts) without full study follow-ups;
Metin 2018	https://dx.doi.org/10.1080/24750573.2018.1465020	Exclusion reason: Study not associated with OCD;
Kilincaslán 2017	https://dx.doi.org/10.1089/cap.2016.0100	Exclusion reason: Repetitive/compulsive behaviour associated with autism spectrum disorders, rather than OCD;
Wilde 2017	https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ridd.2017.03.007	Exclusion reason: Study not associated with OCD;
Park 2017		Exclusion reason: Full text not accessible/retrievable;
DeVries 2017		Exclusion reason: Study not associated with OCD;
Bissell 2016		Exclusion reason: Study not associated with OCD;
Theyel 2015	https://dx.doi.org/10.1038/npp.2015.326	Exclusion reason: Topic not primarily associated with TSC;
D'Antoni 2014	https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.neubiorev.2014.02.003	Exclusion reason: Literature reviews, systematic reviews, meta-analyses, book chapters, conference proceedings, commentaries without primary TAND data;
Khandelwal 2014		Exclusion reason: Grey literature (e.g., conference abstracts) without full study follow-ups;
Jovic 2014	https://dx.doi.org/10.1111/epi.12675	Exclusion reason: Study not associated with OCD;
Latheef 2014	https://dx.doi.org/10.1111/bjd.12986	Exclusion reason: Topic not primarily associated with TSC;
Arbuckle 2013		Exclusion reason: Repetitive/compulsive behaviour associated with autism spectrum disorders, rather than OCD;
Jovic 2012		Exclusion reason: Repetitive/compulsive behaviour associated with autism spectrum disorders, rather than OCD;
Chung 2011		Exclusion reason: OCD grouped within, and its prevalence not distinguished amongst, the broader class of "anxiety disorders";
Maalouf 2010	https://dx.doi.org/10.2217/phe.10.65	Exclusion reason: Literature reviews, systematic reviews, meta-analyses, book chapters, conference proceedings, commentaries without primary TAND data;
Lumsden 2010	https://dx.doi.org/10.1136/adc.2010.186338.24	Exclusion reason: Topic not primarily associated with TSC;
Cabanillas 2009	https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jaad.2008.11.249	Exclusion reason: Topic not primarily associated with TSC;

Folstein 2006	https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cnr.2006.06.008	Exclusion reason: Topic not primarily associated with TSC;
Bardazzi 1998		Exclusion reason: Full text not accessible/retrievable;
Bardazzi 1996	https://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1525-1470.1996.tb01241.x	Exclusion reason: Full text not accessible/retrievable;
Northrup 1993		Exclusion reason: Literature reviews, systematic reviews, meta-analyses, book chapters, conference proceedings, commentaries without primary TAND data;
Yang 2019	https://dx.doi.org/10.1002/jcla.22724	Exclusion reason: Topic not primarily associated with TSC;
Shahid 2013	https://dx.doi.org/10.1111/epi.12458	Exclusion reason: Study not associated with OCD;
Koike-Kumagai 2024	10.1016/j.pbb.2024.173875	Exclusion reason: Study not associated with OCD;
Hsieh 2021	10.1111/bpa.12870	Exclusion reason: Study not associated with OCD;
Flotats-Bastardas 2018	10.1055/s-0038-1637738	Exclusion reason: Study not associated with OCD;
Hsieh 2016	10.1212/CPJ.0000000000000260	Exclusion reason: Literature reviews, systematic reviews, meta-analyses, book chapters, conference proceedings, commentaries without primary TAND data;
Thiele 2014	10.1111/epi.12722	Exclusion reason: Literature reviews, systematic reviews, meta-analyses, book chapters, conference proceedings, commentaries without primary TAND data;
Vigevano 2013	10.1111/epi.12423	Exclusion reason: Topic not primarily associated with TSC;
Yuan 2012	10.1093/hmg/dds262	Exclusion reason: Study not associated with OCD;
Krueger 2011	10.2217/fnl.10.82	Exclusion reason: Literature reviews, systematic reviews, meta-analyses, book chapters, conference proceedings, commentaries without primary TAND data;
Mosconi 2009		Exclusion reason: Topic not primarily associated with TSC;
deVries 2009	10.1002/ajmg.a.32690	Exclusion reason: Study not associated with OCD;
DEB 1998		Exclusion reason: Study not associated with OCD;
Gutierrez 1998		Exclusion reason: Study not associated with OCD;
Bolton 1998		Exclusion reason: OCD without association to TAND topics;
No authorship indicated 2006	https://dx.doi.org/10.1017/S0012162206000880	Exclusion reason: Literature reviews, systematic reviews, meta-analyses, book chapters, conference proceedings, commentaries without primary TAND data;
Kopp 2008	https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.yebeh.2008.05.010	Exclusion reason: Indirect association of TSC and OCD (e.g., OC symptoms in the caregivers of individuals with TSC);

Appendix 13*Quality Assessment of Included Studies*

Author (year)	S1	S2	3.1	3.2	3.3	3.4	3.5	4.1	4.2	4.3	4.4	4.5	Score (0–1.00)
Bhattacharya et al. (2012)	0	0						0	0	1	1	0	0.29
de Vries et al. (2018) ^a	1	1	1	0.5	0	0	1						0.64
Ding et al. (2021) ^a	1	1	1	1	1	1	1						1.00
Fu et al. (2025) ^a	1	1	1	1	1	1	1						1.00
Haddad et al. (2016)	0	0						0	1	0.5	0	0	0.21
Hassan et al. (2014)	0	0						0.5	1	0.5	0	0	0.29
Liu et al. (2020)	1	1	0.5	1	0.5	1	1						0.86
Marcinkowska et al. (2022) ^a	1	1						1	0.5	1	0	1	0.79
Moavero et al. (2022a) ^a	1	1						1	0.5	0.5	1	1	0.86
Moavero et al. (2022b) ^a	1	1						1	0.5	0.5	1	1	0.86
Muzykewicz et al. (2007) ^a	1	1	1	0.5	0.5	1	1						0.86
Ozgur et al. (2018)	1	1						0	1	1	1	0	0.71
Pulsifer et al. (2007) ^a	1	1						1	0.5	1	0.5	1	0.86
Rao et al. (2015)	0	0						0	0	1	1	0	0.29
Vlaskamp et al. (2017)	1	1	0	1	1	0.5	1						0.79
Wilbur et al. (2017) ^a	1	1						1	0.5	0.5	1	0	0.71

Note. Scoring criteria adapted from the Mixed Methods Appraisal Test (MMAT) recommendations and the Vanclooster et al. (2022) study: <0.5 = Low quality; ≥0.5 – <0.75 = Medium quality; ≥0.75 = High quality. Studies are sorted alphabetically by lead author last name, and by date of publication when necessary.

^a = Study included in main meta-analysis

Appendix 14

The Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool, Version 2018 Template

Part I: Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT), version 2018

Category of study designs	Methodological quality criteria	Responses			
		Yes	No	Can't tell	Comments
Screening questions (for all types)	S1. Are there clear research questions?				
	S2. Do the collected data allow to address the research questions?				
	<i>Further appraisal may not be feasible or appropriate when the answer is 'No' or 'Can't tell' to one or both screening questions.</i>				
1. Qualitative	1.1. Is the qualitative approach appropriate to answer the research question?				
	1.2. Are the qualitative data collection methods adequate to address the research question?				
	1.3. Are the findings adequately derived from the data?				
	1.4. Is the interpretation of results sufficiently substantiated by data?				
	1.5. Is there coherence between qualitative data sources, collection, analysis and interpretation?				
2. Quantitative randomized controlled trials	2.1. Is randomization appropriately performed?				
	2.2. Are the groups comparable at baseline?				
	2.3. Are there complete outcome data?				
	2.4. Are outcome assessors blinded to the intervention provided?				
	2.5. Did the participants adhere to the assigned intervention?				
3. Quantitative non-randomized	3.1. Are the participants representative of the target population?				
	3.2. Are measurements appropriate regarding both the outcome and intervention (or exposure)?				
	3.3. Are there complete outcome data?				
	3.4. Are the confounders accounted for in the design and analysis?				
	3.5. During the study period, is the intervention administered (or exposure occurred) as intended?				
4. Quantitative descriptive	4.1. Is the sampling strategy relevant to address the research question?				
	4.2. Is the sample representative of the target population?				
	4.3. Are the measurements appropriate?				
	4.4. Is the risk of nonresponse bias low?				
	4.5. Is the statistical analysis appropriate to answer the research question?				
5. Mixed methods	5.1. Is there an adequate rationale for using a mixed methods design to address the research question?				
	5.2. Are the different components of the study effectively integrated to answer the research question?				
	5.3. Are the outputs of the integration of qualitative and quantitative components adequately interpreted?				
	5.4. Are divergences and inconsistencies between quantitative and qualitative results adequately addressed?				
	5.5. Do the different components of the study adhere to the quality criteria of each tradition of the methods involved?				

Note. Hong QN, Pluye P, Fàbregues S, Bartlett G, Boardman F, Cargo M, Dagenais P, Gagnon M-P, Griffiths F, Nicolau B, O’Cathain A, Rousseau M-C, Vedel I. Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT), version 2018. Registration of Copyright (#1148552), Canadian Intellectual Property Office, Industry Canada.